

Master's Thesis GEO 511

**Acoustic Sensing in Mountain Permafrost:
Designing and Testing a Measurement Assembly**

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Abstract

Rock fracturing due to ice formation and the formation of ice-bonded fracture zones at depth are hypothesized to be relevant preconditioning factors of rock falls in steep permafrost rock-walls as a response to climate change. Most knowledge about the processes associated with the ice-induced rock damage stems from theoretical studies or laboratory experiments. The transfer of corresponding insights to outdoor conditions is nontrivial because there are big spatial variations and temporal fluctuations of surface conditions in high mountain environments. The monitoring of acoustic emissions (AE) is a powerful technique to track the evolution of damage. The investigation of rock damage by AE measurements provides insights into the physical processes. This Master's thesis describes the design of an AE measurement assembly for reliable acquisition of a multi-year time-series in steep alpine rock-walls. Because measurements in steep rock slopes are challenging, this study investigates technical options suitable to capture AE signals from different depths while incurring minimal signal loss between the rock and the sensor. The requirements for the measurement assembly are outlined and different generic solutions are designed and presented. To evaluate and refine them, the coupling of the sensor with the measurement assembly as well as the contact between rock and measurement assembly were explored by determination of the wave attenuation. The determination of speed of sound, acoustic impedance, transmission and attenuation coefficients for different material candidates enabled to choose ideal components of the measurement assembly. Based on argumentation and testing outcomes, the final measurement assembly, called AE-rod, is designed. The AE sensor is inserted directly in the borehole whereby a thin metal plate glued on the rock provides a good contact. A hollow rod as casing protect the AE sensor against external influences and the sealing of the space between rod and rock prevents water flow in the hole. Four prototypes of the AE-rod are installed and tested in a field deployment at 3500 *m.a.s.l.* on Jungfrauoch, Switzerland. The results of first measurements are promising and point to a successful design and construction of the AE-rod.

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Acronyms

AE	acoustic emission
AET	acoustic emission technique
MAGST	mean annual ground surface temperature
MAGT	mean annual ground temperature
MAPT	mean annual permafrost temperature
MARSE	measured area under the rectified signal envelope
MS	micro seismicity
NDT	non-destructive testing
PMUC	produits et matériaux utilisable en centrales (engl.: products and materials used in power plants)
POI	point of interest
POM	polyoxymethylen
POM C	polyoxymethylen copolymer
PU	polyurethane
PZT	plumbum zirconate titanate
TICOP	tenth international conference on permafrost
TIK	Technische Informatik und Kommunikationstechnik (engl.: computer engineering and networks)
WSN	wireless sensor network
ZAA	zero annual amplitude

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Frost weathering and permafrost degradation in high mountains are relevant topics in environmental science because their combination can precondition and trigger natural hazards like debris flows or rock falls and endanger human population as well as infrastructure. Rock fracturing in high mountain environments is mainly driven by volumetric expansion of water during freezing, ice segregation (Akagawa & Fukuda, 1991; Matsuoka & Murton, 2008), thermally induced stress (Hall, 1999) within the rock (Murton, 2007) and erosion or cyclic loading/unloading by glaciers (Prager et al., 2008).

Murton and co-workers (2000; 2001; 2006) have investigated phenomena at some meters depth considering ice segregation in the transient layer, rock falls as result of slope instabilities and thus the impact of these processes on natural hazards. To understand the associated processes and their behavior in field conditions, it is beneficial to investigate them at a small scale because a measurement set-up at shallow depth is easier and less expensive than one for large depth. Hallet and colleagues did this and explored near-surface frost weathering theoretically (e.g., Hallet, 1983; Walder & Hallet, 1985, 1986) as well as experimentally (e.g., Hallet et al., 1991), but their experiment data are constrained to laboratory work and not to field measurements.

Rock damage, especially micro-fracturing activity, can be estimated by measuring acoustic wave emissions. Monitoring acoustic emissions (AE) is a powerful technique which allows detecting, localizing and quantifying damage early, before a crack is visible with the naked eye. AE monitoring facilitates to understand processes under natural conditions near the surface (cm – dm depth). Measuring AE at different depths enables to estimate the depth of the AE source, if it is detectable at least at two sensor positions.

Until now, all investigations about AE in permafrost have been performed in laboratory experiments and the transfer of corresponding insights to natural conditions, involving strong spatial and temporal heterogeneity, is non-

trivial because there are big spatial variations and temporal fluctuations of surface conditions in high mountain environments. Therefore, a proper sampling design and method to assemble an outdoor acoustic sensor system for high mountain areas is important. It enables to connect the knowledge of models and laboratory experiments with field conditions. Hence, the goal of this Master's thesis is designing and testing a measurement assembly for an outdoor wireless acoustic sensing system measuring at different depths. The sensor itself, also referred to as transducer, is a commercial one, the necessary electronics and the data processing have already been produced in a Master's thesis (Hunziker, 2011) at the Computer Engineering and Networks Laboratory (TIK), ETH Zurich (Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich).

1.2 Objective, Aim and Research Questions

This thesis contributes to the long-term objective of studying rock damage dynamics caused by temperature variations and ice formation. The main objective of this thesis is to enable and ascertain high-quality measurements of AE at different depths up to a few decimeters in rock intended to provide a yearlong time-series of AE data in a steep alpine rock-wall. The combination of AE measurements with measurements of its principal controlling factors, temperature and moisture, enables to investigate the cause of rock damage and fracturing in high mountains. For this, the procedure for selection and characterization of the study site as well as a suitable method for the installation of the sensors at depth are important. Systems to measure temperature and moisture at depth exist commercially. The main challenge is to measure the acoustic emissions at depth, because no established measurement system for this exists. Hence, the objective of this thesis is to design and test a suitable measurement assembly for outdoor acoustic sensing. Achieving this aim needs geographic as well as geophysical knowledge and the implementation itself includes technical and engineering aspects. The main scientific aims and questions of this thesis are formulated in the following two points:

- (1) Designing an installation set-up to measure acoustic emission, temperature and moisture at different depths (cm – m).
 - What are the requirements for the desired installation set-up?

- What is the most suitable way to install AE sensors in order to capture the AE signal at various depths?
- How can the sensors be fixed at depth?
- How can repeatable, consistent and reliable measurements be ensured?
- Which components and sensors are necessary?
- Practical recommendation: What steps are needed to allow re-production of such a measurement set-up by others?

(2) Testing and evaluating the developed system.

ERROR SOURCES

- What sources of error or quality loss exist?
- How can they be tested and how large are they?

STRENGTHS, WEAKNESSES AND REMAINING UNCERTAINTIES

- What are the strengths and weaknesses of the developed system?
- What are the limiting factors?

1.3 Context of Project

This thesis is a part of the project *Permasense III*. PermaSense is a collaboration of different engineering and environmental scientists of several Swiss research institutions and companies. The project PermaSense aims at developing and demonstrating a flexible, distributed wireless sensor network (WSN) adapted to geophysical sensors with reliable and high-quality measurement systems for extreme environmental conditions (PermaSense, 2010/2011, access: 16/12/2010). Hasler et al. (2008), Beutel et al. (2009a), Beutel et al. (2009b) and Hasler (2011) showed the concept and architecture of the wireless sensor networks, the data acquisition system and the remote monitoring infrastructure of PermaSense. The project *Permasense III* deals with acoustic sensors for the detection of micro-seismic events and is funded by SNF–NCCR MICS (Swiss National Foundation–National Competence Center in Research on Mobile Information and Communication Systems; www.mics.org) from 2009–2012. This collaboration of different

departments enables to exchange knowledge and to produce high quality measurement systems.

1.4 Requirements

A measurement assembly for sensing AE in mountain permafrost has to meet several requirements. Based on literature research, consultation of experts and discussion with colleagues, the desired characteristics of an operating outdoor system in harsh high-alpine environments are:

1 – Acquire reliable, consistent and repeatable AE measurements

A relevant requirement is acquiring reliable, consistent and repeatable AE measurements with minimal signal loss. The attenuation due to the measurement assembly has to be minimized and it is important that unnecessary damping can be avoided.

2 – Constant coupling between rock and sensor

The quality of the coupling between the rock and the sensor has to be constant over time and over different locations, either if the sensor is coupled directly or indirectly with the rock. External influences like variations of temperature, humidity or other factors should not influence the coupling quality.

3 – Minimal alteration of the site measured

Influences on the *in situ* condition, e.g., due to drilling and changes of the properties like temperature, water permeability or radiation should be minimized. The infiltration of water in the borehole has also to be avoided, since water freezing/thawing can cause spurious AE events (cf. Kaufmann, 1999).

4 – Protection of installation

The installation itself has to be built robustly and has to be protected against environmental influences like water, snow, ice, wind, rock fall, lightning and mountaineers. Otherwise the installation can be damaged or AE of undesired sources can be recorded.

5 – Simple assembly and disassembly of the sensor

Finally, it has to be possible to exchange or retrieve the sensor as easily as possible from the borehole.

1.5 Methodology and Strategy

The methodology and strategy of this Master's thesis is based on a combination of the *Scientific Method* and the *Engineering Design Process*, whereby the motivation and the product are strongly geographically orientated. Figure 1.1 shows the methodology with functional interrelation of the different steps. The definition of aims, research questions and problem statement is the first step. Literature research, consultation of experts and discussion with colleagues enables to define and formulate the requirements (dark-blue box). The *design* step (red box) bases upon the requirements and describes an interaction between the sub-steps *argumentation* and *empirical testing & redesign*. These sub-steps deal with the design of the most suited way to install the AE sensors at various depths. The developed principal ideas and basic concepts are tested and compared with the predefined testing criteria. If necessary, they are redesigned and tested in an iterative loop until they meet the testing criteria. The results of the *design* phase are an argumentation and a testing outcome. These outputs are merged in the *synthesis* step (green box) to the AE measurement assembly. In the final step (light-blue box), this product is characterized.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is divided into different chapters. Chapter 2 gives an overview of permafrost, frost weathering as well as AE and sets the basis of this thesis. In the following Chapter 3, the equipment and methods are presented. The theoretical design of a measurement assembly including argumentation is described in Chapter 4, whereby the laboratory experiments are presented in the Chapter 5. Chapter 6 gives a synthesis of the preceding chapters to the final AE measurement assembly including the description of the field installation and the presentation of first results. In Chapter 7 the preceding chapters are summarized and a perspective is formulated. At the end, the Appendix contains relevant additional information, which is not included in the main document in order to keep the thesis structured. The text will refer to the Appendix wherever needed.

Figure 1.1: Method procedure – combination of *Scientific Method* and *Engineering Design Process*: Functional interrelation of the different steps (colored boxes) and intermediate products (black boxes).

2 Background

This chapter provides the necessary background for the three topics *mountain permafrost*, *weathering* and *acoustic emissions*.

2.1 Mountain Permafrost

«Mountain permafrost is a fascinating phenomenon: It is invisible, extremely variable and heterogeneous, difficult to measure, difficult to model, and it currently undergoes rapid changes.»
Gruber & Haeberli (2009)

Permafrost is ground that remains at or below 0° C for two years or more and forms a layer, centimeters to over a kilometer thick, sandwiched between a seasonally thawed active layer at the surface, and unfrozen ground at depth (Burn, 2007). Figure 2.1a shows the idealized thermal regime of permafrost, with the mean annual ground surface temperature (MAGST), the mean annual ground temperature (MAGT) at the top of permafrost and the mean annual permafrost temperature (MAPT) at the zero annual amplitude (ZAA). The two principal features are a temporal oscillation of the ground temperature in the active layer and an increase in ground temperature with depth (Burn, 2007). Alpine (mountain) permafrost implicitly involves consideration of steep slopes, geographical aspect, solar radiation as well as snow (French, 2007). The thermal conditions of steep bedrock permafrost are influenced by various factors (Figure 2.1c) and are discussed in detail by Hasler (2011).

In many cold mountain areas, permafrost in steep bedrock is abundant and its degradation can cause slope instability that is unexpected and unprecedented in location, magnitude, frequency and timing (Gruber & Haeberli, 2007). Slope instabilities can lead to natural hazards and complicate the operation of infrastructure. Further, wide-spread rock fall, slope instabilities and associated geotechnical problems with human infrastructure seem to be recurrent consequences of warming permafrost in rock-walls due

2 Background

Figure 2.1: (a) Thermal regime of permafrost (from Burn, 2007, modified). (b) Equilibrium temperature field of a cross section through a simplified mountain ridge with 60° steep slopes (from Nötzli, 2008). (c) *Left*: Conceptual model of interactions between atmospheric conditions and rock temperatures at depth; estimations of the net cooling effects with respect to snow free surface are given; in gray, processes with a minor thermal influence ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) are indicated. *Right*: Sketch of rock temperature variability with cooling below snow and beside clefts (blue) and warming at snow free rock surfaces (red) (from Hasler, 2011).

to predicted climatic changes (Gruber et al., 2004). Mountain permafrost features two sliding planes due to the two intersections between frozen and unfrozen ground, namely at the permafrost table at a depth of few meters and at the permafrost base in a ridge at the depth of few ten meters (Figures 2.1a and 2.1b, whereof b shows in black the permafrost base only). They have been hypothesized as exhibiting possible preconditioning due to ice segregation. Hence, knowledge about the distribution and evolution of permafrost temperatures are important for the discernment of sensitive zones (Noetzli et al., 2007). An in-depth investigation of rock deformation, fracturing and motion can be provided by AE monitoring (Section 2.3).

Wegmann et al. (1998) showed with a thermal model approach that «even small amounts of bedrock moisture content will limit the permafrost dynamics to the surface tens of meters at secular time scales». Hence, the moisture content in rock is a relevant factor for temperature and permafrost modeling. However, permafrost degradation in fissured rock-walls reduces the strength and increases the permeability at depth (Haeberli & Beniston, 1998). Nötzli et al. (2007) point that «permafrost degradation in steep topography takes place from different sides, affecting both the permafrost table and the permafrost base. This leads to an increase in the pace of deeper permafrost degradation as compared to permafrost in flat terrain, where warming typically penetrates vertically into the ground». Further, Nötzli & Gruber (2009) conclude that «in connection with possible future warming, latent heat effects considerably modify the pace of permafrost degradation and the pattern of the subsurface temperature field».

2.2 Weathering

«Weathering is the general term applied to the combined action of all processes that cause rock to disintegrate physically and decompose chemically because of exposure near the Earth's surface. ... In *physical weathering*, rocks are fractured and broken apart, primarily by the growth of ice or salt crystals along rock planes and mineral contacts that are penetrated by water solutions. In *chemical weathering*, rock minerals are transformed from types that were stable when the rocks were formed to types that are now stable at surface temperatures and pressures.»

Strahler & Strahler (2005)

We can distinguish the physical weathering in frost weathering and non-frost weathering (Table 2.1). For this thesis, the weathering processes and mechanisms in high mountains or in cold regions are relevant. Rock weathering in high mountains can mainly be caused by *thermally induced stress* (cf. Hall & André, 2001; Murton, 2007) or *frost weathering*. The frost weathering itself can be caused by the processes *volume expansion* and *ice segregation*. Table 2.2 shows the history of frost-weathering studies.

Table 2.1: Physical weathering processes.

<i>Frost weathering</i>	<i>Non-frost weathering</i>
– volume expansion	– hydration shattering
– ice segregation	– thermally induced stress
	– salt weathering

The *volume expansion* explains the phenomenon when water turns into ice and expands by 9%. This phase change leads to an increase of the pressure in the water-filled spaces of the rock. If the pores are completely water saturated and the water freezes *in situ*, at a temperature of -22°C the ice formation can theoretically cause pressure up to 207 MPa, which is one to two magnitudes higher than the tensile strength of rock (Matsuoka & Murton, 2008). However, rock damaging caused by volume expansion can only be observed if there is a high degree of water saturation to avoid compensation by compression of air (Murton, 2007), rapid cooling from all sides to freeze the water in situ (Matsuoka & Murton, 2008) and a low drainage ability (Wegmann, 1998). Figure 2.2 shows the influence of the ice saturation and the drainage ability on the rock fracturing caused by volume expansion.

Already in the 1920s and 1930s, Stephen Taber (1929, 1930) showed with laboratory experiments and field observations that the frost damage and the frost heave phenomenon can not only be explained with volume expansion and suggested a combination of different processes.

The *ice segregation* describes the combination of the processes water migration, cryosuction and volume expansion. Cryosuction describes the transport of liquid water through porous media to the freezing site due to temperature-gradient induced suction and the suction generated by the un-

Table 2.2: Advances in frost-weathering studies (from Matsuoka & Murton, 2008).

Year	Field		Theory
	Visual evidence	Measurement/ monitoring	
1900	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Shattered bedrock/clasts – Block field – Talus below rock cliff – Strandflat 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Volumetric expansion (incl. hydrofracture)
1950	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cryoplanation terrace – Rockwall retreat 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rock falls – Rock temperature (seasonal) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Simulating microgelivation – Capillary theory
1970		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rock mass strength – Rock temperature (all year) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Unfrozen water in subfreezing rock
1980	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Bedrock heave – Lacustrine platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rock moisture – Bedrock disintegration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rock properties – Ice segregation and crack propagation
1990	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – New crack growth in clasts – Brecciated bedrock 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Simulating ice segregation (frost/thaw depth)
2000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Large-scale rock falls/avalanches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Rock joint fracturing – 2-D moisture distribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Centrifuge modeling of rock slip – Simulating bidirectional freezing – Numerical modeling (3-D thermal field, bedrock disintegration and slope evolution)

2-D = two dimensional; 3-D = three dimensional.

Figure 2.2: For frost weathering by volume expansion, there has to be high water saturation and a low hydraulic drainage during freezing of the pore water (from Wegmann, 1998, redrawn and translated).

frozen water held in capillaries and adsorbed on the surfaces on mineral particles (Murton, 2007). By modifying the *Clausius-Clapeyron Equation* (Eq. A.1), Williams & Smith (1989) have calculated the cryosuction as follows:

$$dP_w = \frac{\rho_w \cdot dT \cdot L_f}{T} \quad (2.1)$$

where dT is the lowering of the freezing point, L_f is the latent heat of fusion, T is the absolute temperature and ρ_w is the density of water. Equation 2.1 indicates that the lowering of the freezing point of each °C below 0° C induces a cryosuction of 1.2 MPa (Murton, 2007).

The freezing of the migrated water at the freezing site results in lenses or layers of segregated ice due to ice growth (Matsuoka & Murton, 2008). Figure 2.3 shows a simplified sketch of the ice segregation model, whereby an unfrozen water film between ice and rock is visible (cf. Mellor, 1970) but the temporal change of permeability and temperature gradients is missing.

The two classical frost weathering processes are compared in Table 2.3. Very often, there is a combination of these two processes and it is mostly not

Figure 2.3: For frost weathering by ice segregation, the temperature gradient has to be constant that water can migrate to the freezing site (based on Wegmann, 1998, redrawn and translated [based on Hallet, 1983, modified]).

possible to distinguish them. Wegmann (1998) could show that the process dominance might be depth dependent. Volume expansion can be observed close to the surface (mm – m) during frost cycles and can cause rock fall. In contrast, ice segregation appears at depth (dm – hm) over years and can precondition big rock fall and landslide.

A controlling factor for the two frost weathering processes is the availability of water, especially the degree of saturation before freezing and the amount of water migration during freezing. Matsuoka (2001) investigated this with laboratory experiments and summarized the influence of the moisture availability on frost weathering of a partially frozen rock (Figure 2.4) as follows:

«If the water table is too deep, water migration from the underlying unfrozen part would be minimum so that an initial water content in excess of S_{CR} (critical degree of saturation above which frost weathering is active; it varies from 58% to 93%, but mainly falls around 80%) is required for significant expansion (model A). In contrast, where the water table is shallow, water migration from the saturated zone eventually raises the water content of the frozen part above S_{CR} and subsequent prolonged ice segregation would induce expansion much larger than expected from full saturation (model B). Volumetric expansion

Table 2.3: Comparison of frost weathering models (from Hallet et al., 1991).

<i>Volumetric-expansion model</i>	<i>Segregation ice model</i>
No frost weathering if pore fluid contracts upon freezing	Frost weathering does not depend on the volumetric expansion of water during freezing
No frost weathering under conditions common in nature: saturation level less than about 91%, and pores not effectively sealed off (hydraulically closed system)	Saturation level influences rate of water migration in hydraulically connected pores (open system). Low saturation does not preclude water migration and crack growth
Water may be expelled from freezing sites, but never drawn towards such sites	Water attraction to freezing sites, due to chemical potential gradients, is a key factor in frost weathering. If crack growth cannot accommodate water-to-ice expansion, water is expelled from freezing sites
Crack growth should occur in bursts as water freezes and expands	Slow, steady crack growth should occur as water migrates towards ice bodies within cracks. Predicted crack growth rates are compatible with values inferred from experimental data
No clear prediction of role of environmental conditions or material parameters	Specific prediction of the role of environmental conditions and material parameters emanates from the model and guides experimental work
A variety of other possible mechanisms of frost weathering are viewed as essentially independent	Various mechanisms of frost weathering may be unified within a framework of fracture-mechanical principles

associated with rapid (diurnal) freezing favors model A, while ice segregation associated with slow (seasonal or inter-annual) freezing plays a major role in model B. The transition from model A to B depends on how high the capillarity or adsorption can draw water from the saturated zone to the frozen rock. Laboratory simulations show that the frozen part draws water from the water table at least shallower than 10 cm; the critical height is unlikely to be greater than a few decimeters, reflecting the low permeability of rocks.»

Matsuoka (2001)

Figure 2.4: Summary of the influence of moisture availability on frost weathering of a rock undergoing downward freezing. The influence of (A) deep and (B) shallow water levels on frost weathering of a rock undergoing downward freezing with the initial degree of saturation, S_0 (from Matsuoka, 2001, redrawn).

2.3 Acoustic Emissions

Acoustic emission (AE) refers to the generation of transient elastic waves produced by a sudden redistribution of stress in a material (NDT Resource Center, 2010/2011, access: 18/11/2010). AE can be considered to be a form of micro-seismicity (MS) generated during the failure process as materials are loaded (Grosse, 2008). Generally, AE can be detected in many deformation processes in which dislocations play no role. However, in homogeneous deformations which involve dislocations, acoustic emissions correlate with the apparent motion of the dislocations (Gillis, 1972).

AE are more strongly dependent on the irreversible (non-elastic) deformations in a material. Therefore, capture of AE allows detecting the formation of new cracks and the progression of existing cracks or friction processes. These phenomena are often related to internal mechanical or thermal loads or pressures applied from outside the specimen (Grosse, 2008).

Hardy (2003) summarizes the AE/MS basic concept as follows:

1. The AE/MS technique is a passive, indirect technique.
2. AE/MS activity originates as an elastic stress wave at locations where the material is mechanically unstable.
3. The associated stress wave propagates through the surrounding material undergoing attenuation as it moves away from the source.
4. With suitable instrumentation, AE/MS activity may be detected at locations in a considerable distance from the source.
5. The usable spatial range of the technique is dependent on the frequency content of the source and the characteristics of the media and the monitoring facility.
6. The character of the observed AE/MS signals provides indirect evidence of the type and degree of the associated instability.
7. Analysis of data obtained from a number of transducers (array) make it possible to determine the actual location (i.e., spatial coordinates) of the source.

These points are going to be further discussed in this section.

2.3.1 Scientific Context

The detection of micro-cracking activity in rock using acoustic emissions has started 50 years ago, and has been used in the lab to monitor the development of cracks in freezing rocks (Hallet et al., 1991). AE is generated by inelastic deformation in rocks and is related to damage increase or to shearing of existing fractures (Scholz, 1968). AE provides insight into the physical processes that control sliding and slope failure (Spillmann, 2007). In cold rock-walls, the mechanical loading of rock, which involves local inelastic deformations, results from the combination of a constant gravity load and fluctuating loads related to (1) thermal stresses, arising from the heterogeneities in the temperature field, (2) pressure variations in rock pores and cracks, due to water or to ice formation and (3) short-term external loading such as earthquakes (Amitrano et al., 2011).

Walder & Hallet (1985) predicted theoretically, that crack growth may be quite rapid for constant crack-wall temperatures in the range -4°C to -15°C , if ample water is available. They also found that the crack growth does not require temperature oscillating around 0°C . Hallet et al. (1991) confirmed this in an experimental study and concluded that freezing-induced fracture propagation events are not associated with the nominal freezing because most fracture activity occurs at distinctly lower temperatures between -3°C and -6°C and continues under sustained freezing conditions.

AE monitoring has been extensively used at the laboratory rock sample scale (Lockner, 1993) or at a larger scale to monitor seismicity, rock bursts in mines and tunnels, as well as slope instabilities (Amitrano et al., 2005). Amitrano et al. (2010) have monitored the rock instability and deformation at a high alpine ridge with the acoustic emission/micro-seismic (AE/MS) activity investigation technique. Their first observations and analysis have shown, that the monitoring system can detect noise generated by rock slope deformation. Based on a four-day experiment in spring 2011 on Jungfrau-joch, Amitrano et al. (2011) recently showed that the AE signal monitored at the rock surface in high-altitude rock-wall could also be used to investigate rock damage induced by temperature variations and freezing. For bigger scale and lower frequencies, Schneider (2011) showed that seismic signals can be used in rapid mass movement analysis and are suitable for early warning systems of debris flows, lahars or pyroclastic flows.

Apart from that, at the moment, there are no measurements of ultrasonic frequency AE under real conditions in high mountain permafrost and the link between laboratory results and real conditions is not explored.

2.3.2 Acoustic Emission Technique (AET)

The acoustic emission technique (AET) is a non-destructive testing (NDT) method which can be used either to monitor changes in materials behavior over a long time without moving one of its components (i.e. sensors) or to characterize materials (Grosse & Ohtsu, 2008). It applies to laboratory as well as to field studies in the geotechnical area (Hardy, 2003). But it is limited to small-scale investigations with dimensions of a few meters, because typical AE are in the kHz range, a frequency band that is strongly attenuated in fractured rock (Spillmann, 2007). Emission sources can be evaluated through the study of their intensity and arrival time to collect information about the sources of the energy (NDT Resource Center, 2010/2011, access: 18/11/2010). The ability to detect crack propagation occurring not only on the surface but also deep inside a material makes the AET quite unique (Grosse & Ohtsu, 2008). A reliable analysis of acoustic emission signals and the interpretation of the data in material testing are usually only possible in cases where the signals have been localized successfully (Grosse, 2008). Localization of the sources can be obtained from AE data using the arrival-time difference method (Rindorf, 1984).

A short overview of sources, signals, advantages and challenges of the AET is given here, based on the extensive texts by Demtröder (2008), Grosse (2008) and Hardy (2003).

Sources and signals of AE

The AE appears to be related to processes of deformation and failure which cause rapid release of localized strain energy of stressed material. This energy release can be due to, for example, micro-cracking in the material. AE activity in polycrystalline materials can be generated at different levels: (1) at the micro-level as a result of dislocations, (2) at the macro-level by grain boundary movement or initiation and propagation of fractures through and between mineral grains and (3) at the mega-level by relative motion between structural units or fracturing and failure of large areas of material.

Using a suitable transducer, the generated elastic stress wave, which travels from the point of origin within the material to the sensor position, can be observed as an AE/MS signal or a discrete AE/MS event. Usually, the most AE/MS signals or events contain compressional (P-wave) and shear (S-wave) components, which are difficult to distinguish in some cases. The characteristics of the source as well as the distance and the material between the source and the monitoring transducer determine the frequency character of the observed AE/MS signals and events. The frequency domain varies from below 1 Hz (large scale field site) to above 500 kHz (laboratory), depending on the observation scale. Figure 2.5 shows the frequency domain used for AET. The overall frequency domain can basically be split into four main groups: (1) subsonic sound/infrasound with $\nu < 16$ Hz, (2) audible acoustic sound with $16 \text{ Hz} < \nu < 16 \text{ kHz}$, (3) ultrasonic sounds with $16 \text{ kHz} < \nu < 10 \text{ MHz}$ and (4) hypersound with $\nu > 10 \text{ MHz}$. More information about the technical context is given in the Section 2.3.3.

Due to significant differences in the AE sources, the AE signals can have widely varying characteristics. Continuous emission (e.g., produced during metal cutting) show very different signal characteristics when compared to burst signals (e.g., caused by spontaneous release of energy during cracking; see Figure 2.6). Most techniques used for measuring AE are better suited for burst signals than for continuous emission of acoustic waves.

Advantages of AET

An advantage of AE techniques, compared to other non-destructive testing techniques (e.g., RADAR, X-ray, ultrasonic and infra-red images), is that damage processes in materials being tested can be observed during the entire load history, without any disturbance to the specimen. Under favorable conditions only a few sensors are required to monitor the AE activity. Further, access to both sides of an object, which is necessary for all through-transmission methods, is not required in AET.

The ability to delineate the area of instability is another major advantage of the AET compared to other geotechnical monitoring tech-

2 Background

Figure 2.5: Frequency domain of AET (based on Hardy, 2003, redrawn and slightly modified). *Top*: Frequency domains over which AE/MS and other associated studies have been conducted; *Bottom*: Typical spatial range vs. frequency data for AE/MS signals.

Figure 2.6: Example of burst signals compared to a continuous emission of acoustic waves (from Grosse, 2008).

niques. There are two main reasons, why an accurate AE/MS source location can be relevant: (1) if the exact source location is not known, it is only possible to get the relative magnitude of an observed AE/MS event instead of the true one, and (2) it is necessary to know the exact source location to determine the mechanism responsible for the observed activity. The spatial coordinates of the AE/MS source can be determined by spatial calculations using the difference in arrival-time between the different transducers and the velocity of propagation in the material. Figure 2.7 shows the technique for point location. Depending on the order of point location, signals must be detected in a minimum number of sensors: two for linear, three for planar, four for volumetric.

Challenges of AET

A relevant disadvantage of the AET method is that a particular test is not perfectly reproducible due to the nature of the signal source, e.g., the sudden and sometimes random formation of a crack. Therefore, the results have to be interpreted very carefully.

Another point addresses the energy released by an acoustic emission. Very sensitive sensors as well as reliable amplifiers are required, because signals – in particular those emitted as precursors of failure – are usually several magnitudes smaller compared to signals used in ultrasonic techniques.

Figure 2.7: Technique for point location of an AE source: The velocity of wave propagation and exact position of the sensors are necessary criteria. Equations can then be derived using sensor array geometry or more complex algebra to locate the source (from NDT Resource Center, 2010/2011, access: 18/11/2010, redrawn).

2.3.3 Technical Context: Energy Transmission and Detection

The particle motion at the transducers is dependent on factor group A (see the left column of Table 2.4) which have a direct or indirect influence on the propagation of the elastic waves generated by the source as well as on factor group B (see the right column of Table 2.4) which generally influence the generation and propagation of these waves (Hardy, 2003).

Table 2.4: Factors which affect the particle motion at the transducer (factor group A) and factors which influence the propagation of waves (factor group B).

<i>Factor group A</i>	<i>Factor group B</i>
– form and energy level of the source	– type of wave propagation
– geometry of the test structure	– propagation velocities
– mechanical properties of the associated media	– reflection and refraction at boundaries and interfaces
– type and degree of discontinuities	– wave attenuation

A few of these factors are discussed to improve the comprehension of the

process which happens between the source (structural instability) and the transducer (actual monitoring site) as follows, based on the extensive texts by Demtröder (2008), Hardy (2003) and NDT Resource Center (2010/2011, access: 27/09/2011).

Body and surface waves

We can distinguish two types of elastic waves. The *body waves* travel through the interior of a material and are progressive excitations of ground volume elements involving elastic dilatations (particle motion in direction of propagation) and distortions (particle motion perpendicular to direction of propagation). Compressional waves can also be called longitudinal waves, dilatational waves, pressure waves, irrotational waves, primary or P-waves and shear waves can also be called transverse waves, distortional waves, secondary or S-waves. The *surface waves* (including Rayleigh and Love waves) are plane waves and travel along the material surface. With respect to P- and S-waves, surface waves often have large amplitudes but their velocities are lower and therefore they arrive later.

Wave propagation

The energy from a seismic source can propagate as plane, cylindrical or spherical waves. The wave mode depends on the dimensioning of the source with respect to the full sample. Cylindrical waves are generated by seismic line sources whereas spherical waves are generated by seismic point sources. Due to the fact that the associated energy must be distributed over an area that increases proportional to the radius r from the source (surface area of cylindrical wave front = $2\pi rl$; surface area of spherical wave front = $4\pi r^2$) and the fact that the energy in the elastic wave is proportional to the square of its amplitude ($\epsilon \propto A^2$), the observed wave amplitude will fall off as $1/r^{1/2}$ for cylindrical waves and $1/r$ for spherical waves. Therefore, the wave amplitude A at a radius r from the source can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cylindrical wave :} \quad A = A_0/r^{1/2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{Spherical wave :} \quad A = A_0/r \quad (2.3)$$

where A_0 is the wave amplitude at the source and r is the distance from the source.

Seismic velocities

Compressibility and shear characteristics of the propagation medium influence the velocity of an elastic wave. With the assumption of isotropic and homogeneous elasticity of the medium, the velocity of compressional elastic body waves (C_1) and the velocity of the shear waves (C_2) can theoretically be calculated:

$$C_1 = \sqrt{(\lambda + 2\mu)/\rho} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad C_1 = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho} \left\{ \frac{1 - \nu}{(1 - 2\nu)(1 + \nu)} \right\}} \quad (2.4)$$

$$C_2 = \sqrt{\mu/\rho} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad C_2 = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho} \left\{ \frac{1}{2(1 + \nu)} \right\}} \quad (2.5)$$

λ	first Lamé constant	
μ	second Lamé constant	
ρ	mass density	
E	Young's modulus	$\rightarrow E = \mu(3\lambda + 2\mu)/(\lambda + \mu)$
ν	Poisson's ratio	$\rightarrow \nu = 0.5\lambda/(\lambda + \mu)$

The seismic velocities will be influenced by the direction of propagation, if the medium is anisotropic. Table 2.5 shows typical seismic velocities of different media.

Acoustic impedance

The acoustic impedance of a material is defined as the product of its density ρ and wave velocity C :

$$Z = \rho C \quad (2.6)$$

Since the velocity can be differentiated between P- and S-wave velocity, an isotropic material has two specific acoustic impedance values:

$$\text{Acoustic impedance of } P\text{-wave :} \quad Z_1 = \rho C_1 \quad (2.7)$$

$$\text{Acoustic impedance of } S\text{-wave :} \quad Z_2 = \rho C_2 \quad (2.8)$$

Table 2.5 shows typical values for Z_1 .

Table 2.5: Typical values of P-wave and S-wave velocities (C_1 and C_2), density (ρ) as well as typical values of acoustic impedance associated with P-wave propagation (Z_1). These values are only approximate, since they are sensitive to the state of stress, temperature, composition, mechanical history and mechanical state of each material (based on Rinehart, 1975; Milsom, 1996; Hardy, 2003, and other sources, selected and extended).

<i>Material</i>	C_1 [m/s]	C_2 [m/s]	ρ [kg/dm ³]	Z_1 [10 ⁶ kg/(s · m ²)]
Aluminum	6100	3100	2.7	16.47
Brass	4300	2000	8.4	36.12
Steel ^a	5800	3100	7.8	45.24
Lead	2200	700	11.3	24.86
Plexiglass	2600	1300	1.2	3.12
Air	331	— ^b	0.0013	0.00043
Water	1483	— ^b	1.0	1.49
Ice	3200	1920 ^c	0.92	2.44
Granite	5000	3000 ^c	2.7	13.50
Gneiss	6000	3600 ^c	2.7	16.20
Limestone	3200	1920 ^c	2.3	7.36
Sandstone	2000	1200 ^c	2.1	4.20
Basalt	5400	3240 ^c	2.86	15.44
Shale	2250	1350 ^c	2.51	5.65

^a Mild steel and chromium steel

^b Fluids do not support shear stress

^c Computed from C_1 data assuming $C_2/C_1 = 0.6$

Effects at boundaries

The transmission of AE/MS energy through a composite structure (e.g., layered media) is influenced critically by variations in acoustic impedance due to the reflection and refraction that result at boundaries between areas having different values of acoustic impedance. When the acoustic impedance of the two different areas (Z_1 and Z'_1) are known, the *reflection coefficient* can be calculated as follows:

$$R = \left(\frac{Z'_1 - Z_1}{Z'_1 + Z_1} \right)^2 \quad (2.9)$$

which shows the fraction of the incident wave intensity that is reflected. Due to the fact that the amount of incident energy minus reflected energy must equal the amount of transmitted energy, the *transmission coefficient* can be calculated as follows:

$$T = 1 - R \quad (2.10)$$

The behavior of plane waves at cohesive and non-cohesive boundaries is explained in the following text.

Normal incidence-cohesive boundary

In this case, the angle of incidence $\alpha = 0$. Figure 2.8a shows the normal incidence of a compressional wave on boundary between two different materials. The amplitude of the incident stress wave σ_I can be calculated as:

$$\sigma_I + \sigma_R = \sigma_T \quad (2.11)$$

where the amplitudes of the transmitted (σ_T) and reflected waves (σ_R) are:

$$\sigma_T = \left(\frac{2Z'_1}{Z'_1 + Z_1} \right) \sigma_I \quad (2.12)$$

$$\sigma_R = \left(\frac{Z'_1 - Z_1}{Z'_1 + Z_1} \right) \sigma_I \quad (2.13)$$

Oblique incidence-cohesive boundary

If the angle of incidence $\alpha \neq 0$, longitudinal and shear wave components are involved and transmission (refraction) as well as reflection

of energy can be observed. Figure 2.8b shows a P-wave (P_I) incident on the boundary of two materials with an oblique angle, which generates either a transmitted and reflected P-wave (P_T and P_R) as well as S-wave (S_T and S_R) with the following relationship between these four stress wave components:

$$\frac{1}{C_1} \cdot \sin \alpha = \frac{1}{C_2} \cdot \sin \beta = \frac{1}{C'_1} \cdot \sin \eta = \frac{1}{C'_2} \cdot \sin \xi \quad (2.14)$$

where α , β , η and ξ are the angles of incidence, reflection and re-refraction. Because the velocities and the acoustic impedances change at the cohesive boundary (e.g., glue or couplant of the measurement system), there exist critical angles over which no transmission can be observed anymore.

Oblique incidence-noncohesive boundary

These conditions and the resulting effect on the wave propagation are of importance in fractured rock masses, but cannot be discussed here, because it is a substantial theory that does not allow a simple and reasonable parameterization (see Egle, 1987; Rinehart, 1975).

Figure 2.8: Incidence of a compressional wave on a cohesive boundary between two different materials (from Hardy, 2003, redrawn). (a) Normal incidence of a compressional wave on boundary between two materials having different acoustic impedances. (b) Oblique incidence of a compressional wave on a boundary between two materials having different values of C_1 and C_2 .

Stress wave attenuation

Attenuation describes the loss of signal amplitude or energy per unit area due to different factors, especially:

Geometric spreading

This factor is already explained in the paragraph «Wave propagation» on page 23.

Internal friction

Energy is absorbed and lost due to internal friction caused by effects such as hysteresis and viscoelastic damping. This loss of energy can be described with the following relationship:

$$A = A_0 e^{-\alpha r} \quad (2.15)$$

where α corresponds to the attenuation coefficient and is considered to be a function of frequency.

The combination of the two factors geometric spreading and internal friction result in:

$$A = A_0(e^{-\alpha r}/r) \quad (2.16)$$

Scattering

Scattering is a phenomenon in polycrystalline materials where the wavelength λ of the stress wave (with propagation velocity C and frequency f) features the grain size (with mean diameter d) of the material:

$$d \approx \lambda \quad (2.17)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{C}{f} \quad (2.18)$$

In this case a secondary wave is generated at the grain position which spreads out in different directions causing an attenuation of the signal.

Mode conversion

The generation of a variety of refracted and reflected components due to a stress wave incident on a cohesive or noncohesive boundary (see section «Effects at Boundaries» on page 26) is called mode conversion. It causes a reduction of the level of outgoing energy and of the stress wave amplitude.

2.3.4 Technology, Electronics and Acoustic Emission Analysis

Sensors technology and couplants

The mechanical energy associated with an AE/MS event can be converted into a suitable electrical signal by a transducer (Hardy, 2003). AE sensors have been commercially available for more than thirty years (Vahaviolos, 1998). Depending on the frequency domain, different kinds of sensors or transducers are used, whereby the basic sensitivity versus frequency characteristics of the different transducer types must also be considered in regard to the selection of the optimum type (Hardy, 2003):

- *Displacement gages* are most efficient in the low frequencies (e.g., $0.01\text{ Hz} - 1.0\text{ Hz}$).
- *Velocity gages (geophones)* are most efficient in the intermediate frequency domain (e.g., $1.0\text{ Hz} - 5\text{ kHz}$).
- *Accelerometers* are most efficient in the high frequencies (e.g., $5\text{ kHz} - 500\text{ kHz}$).

Velocity gages or accelerometers are normally used in AE/MS studies. Different types of accelerometers exist: piezoelectric sensors, optical fiber sensors as well as sensors based on laser systems (Ohtsu, 2008). In this thesis, piezoelectric sensors are used because of their easy application and their high sensitivity (Section 3.1 gives detailed information about the used equipment).

«In the case of piezoelectric or PZT (Plumbum Zirconate Titanate) sensors, the sensors are usually operated in resonance. ... Very damped sensors are operated outside their resonance frequencies allowing a broadband detection, although they are usually less sensitive to wave motions.»
Ohtsu (2008)

Figure 2.9 shows a schematic representation of a piezoelectric sensor which is directly attached to the surface of the material sample. The piezoelectric element in the housing case enables to detect and measure AE waves, based on the piezoelectric effect out of lead zirconate titanate (Ohtsu, 2008).

Figure 2.9: Schematic representation of a piezoelectric sensor (based on NDT Resource Center, 2010/2011, access: 03/08/2011, redrawn and modified).

«Piezoelectricity is linear interaction between mechanical and electrical systems in non-centric crystals and similar structures. The direct piezoelectric effect may be defined as the change of electric polarization proportional to the strain. ... Piezoelectric devices have the ability to convert mechanical strain into an electrical charge when used as sensor, and to do the opposite when used as an actuator.»
Tichý et al. (2010)

For obtaining a good measurement, correct coupling of an AE sensor to the material sample is essential. A couplant is a substance that is positioned between the AE sensor and the medium. The main task of a couplant is to remove the air between the material sample and the AE sensor, because air has very low acoustic impedance (412 Nsm^{-3}) and thus decreases the transmission substantially (NPL, 2011, access: 20/10/2011). Hence, a couplant (typically liquid, gel, wax or grease) should have a similar acoustic impedance compared to the material being tested, bond the sensor to the material so that the loss of energy is reduced and the total volume of air bubbles between the sensor and the structure is minimized (Grosse & Linzer, 2008).

Electronics, data acquisition and data processing

The electronics, data acquisition and data processing, which is used

for the field experiments of this thesis, was provided by the Master's thesis of Josua Hunziker (Hunziker, 2011). He explored the possibilities of acquiring sensor data at high sampling rates with a focus on the application of AE measurements on rock-walls and presented a prototype of an AE sensing system.

Acoustic emission analysis: parameter-based and signal-based

Recording and analyzing AE signals can be divided into two main groups, namely parameter-based (classical) and signal-based (quantitative) AET (Grosse & Linzer, 2008). Table 2.6 summarizes the attributes of the different methods, whereby the discrepancies between the two approaches are becoming smaller as technology improves.

Table 2.6: Comparison of the two AE techniques (from Grosse & Linzer, 2008).

	<i>Parameter-based AET</i>	<i>Signal-based AET</i>
Failure detection	Large scale	Small scale
Localization:		
– 1D (zonal)	requires many sensors	requires many sensors
– 2D (planar)	minimum 3 sensors	minimum 3 sensors
– 3D	minimum 4 sensors	minimum 4 sensors
Fast real-time data analysis	requires PC with memory	—
Statistical analysis	requires PC with memory	requires PC with memory
Analysis of:		
– amplitudes	Only statistical analysis	resolution > 12 Bit
– frequencies	—	requires broadband sensors
– waveforms	—	sampling frequency > 1 MHz
Fracture analysis	—	Min. 6 sensors in the farfield
– Fault-plane orientation	—	Distributed sensors
– Fault-plane size	—	Moment tensor inversion
– Fault-plane energy	—	Moment tensor inversion
– Fracture mode (I, II, III, mixed)	—	Moment tensor inversion

For this thesis, the parameter-based technique is used, but the original signal is recorded as well. To extract parametric AE features, the signal has to be analyzed. At first, for the distinction of an AE event from background noise, a threshold of AE wave amplitude has to be set. If signals exceed this threshold, they are identified as AE signals and the following AE parameters can be identified (Shiotani, 2008; NDT Resource Center, 2010/2011, access: 18/11/2010):

- 1 – Hit** is a signal that exceeds the threshold and causes the AE system to accumulate data.
- 2 – Amplitude A** is the peak voltage of the signal waveform, often expressed in decibels (dB) where $A^{\text{dB}} = 20 \cdot \log_{10}(A^{\text{V}})$. This is an important parameter in AE inspection because it determines the detectability of the signal.
- 3 – Duration D** is the time between the first and last threshold crossings. The duration is expressed generally in microseconds and can be used to identify different types of sources as well as to filter out noise.
- 4 – Rise Time R** is the time between the first threshold crossing and the peak amplitude. Rise time can be used for qualification of signals and as a criterion for a noise filter, because it is closely related to the source-time function (propagation of the wave between the source of the AE event and the sensor).
- 5 – Pre- & posttrigger time** is a defined time range before and after the AE signal crosses the threshold. These two parameter are not used in this thesis.
- 6 – Count N** is the number of times within the duration an AE event signal exceeds the threshold.

Figure 2.10 shows these conventional AE signal features. Further useful features derived by calculations are (Shiotani, 2008):

- 7 – Energy E** of an AE signal is defined in different ways, but generally as the sum of the squared sample amplitudes or the measured area under the rectified signal envelope (MARSE).
- 8 – Average frequency** is the ratio $\frac{\text{Count}}{\text{Duration}}$ of one AE hit.

9 – RA value is defined as the reciprocal of gradient in AE signal waveforms and is given by the ratio $\frac{\text{Rise time}}{\text{Amplitude}}$. It enables to classify the type of cracks (e.g., tensile crack vs. shear crack).

Figure 2.10: Conventional AE signal features. The blue part of the AE signal curve is the analyzed one (based on Shiotani, 2008, redrawn and modified).

3 Equipment and Methods

This chapter is divided in two main parts. In the first section, the used equipment for the experimental tests and the final installation set-up is shown. In the second section, the relevant methods of this thesis are described.

3.1 Equipment

The main used equipment is briefly described in the following description:

Acoustic emission

Table 3.1 gives an overview of the used AE equipment in the lab and field. The type of the AE sensor was chosen based on the experience of Amitrano et al. (2011). The electronics and data processing for the acoustic emissions were developed by Josua Hunziker as a Master's thesis (Hunziker, 2011) and improved by Roman Lim at the Computer Engineering and Networks Laboratory (TIK), ETH Zurich (Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich). Detailed information (specification sheet or product bulletin) is given in the Appendix A.6.

Moisture

The commercial capacitive *Sentek EnviroSMART* sensor system is used to measure the volumetric water content at depth. Figure 3.1 shows the attachment of the capacitance sensor to a probe with integrated circuits for signal processing and analog to digital conversion as well as a close-up view of the ring-capacitor sensor (Schwank et al., 2006). For further detailed information, please check the instruction manual (Scientific Inc., 2009), the official homepage of Sentek Sensor Technologies (www.sentek.com.au) or the publication of Schwank et al. (2006).

Table 3.1: Acoustic emission equipment.

Type	Model	Description	Employment
Sensor	<i>R60</i> ^a	Frequency AE sensor; General purpose; 60 kHz resonant	Lab
Sensor	<i>PK6J</i> ^a	Resonant AE sensor; Medium frequency integral preamplifier	Lab
Sensor	<i>R6TG – TC</i> ^a	<i>R60</i> -crystal integrated in the housing of <i>R15TG – TC</i> with a <i>BNC</i> plug	Field
Amplifier	<i>IL – LP6S</i> ^a	Small (1" × 1" × 2.2"), low cost «In-Line» preamplifiers for 60 kHz sensors	Lab & Field
USB AE Node	<i>USB AE Node</i> ^a	Easy laptop & PC connection and low cost AE system	Lab
Software	<i>AEwin</i> ^a	For true, real time windows operation and control of AE system	Lab
Pulser/Actuator	<i>FieldCAL</i> ^a	Acoustic emission hand-held; battery powered signal generator	Lab & field
AE-box	Prototype ^b	Electronics, data acquisition and data processing	Field

^a Distributor & Manufacturer: Mistras & Physical Acoustic Corporation

^b Producer: J. Hunziker & TIK

Figure 3.1: *Sentek EnviroSMART* sensor system (from Schwank et al., 2006). (a) EnviroSMART water content probe with capacitance sensors (right) and access tube (left) . (b) Sensors with symbolized field lines. (c) Sensor electronic board, whereby the external capacitance C is a function of the permittivity ϵ of the medium surrounding the access tube.

Temperature

The commercial *Th3 Soil Temperature Profile Probe* from UMS is used to measure the temperature profile at six different depths (5, 10, 20, 30, 50 and 100 cm). The six temperature sensor elements are placed at the different depths inside a tube made of glass-fiber reinforced plastic. Detailed information are given in the user manual (Steins & Keller, 2010) or on the official homepage of UMS (www.ums-muc.de/en/products/soil_temperature/th3.html).

WSN system

The entire chain from sensing over data logging and transmission to data management is provided by the *WSN system* of *PermaSense*.

Drilling

The equipment to drill the installation holes for the final field deployment was rented from the company Blétry AG.

3.2 Methods

This section shows the used methods to generate and measure AE signal, to determine the acoustic characteristics of different materials and media, to use statistical sizes as well as to characterize the field site.

3.2.1 AE: Generating and Measuring Signals

Generating AE (*Method 1*)

Three options to generate artificial AE signals are used.

Pulser (Method 1a)

Pulser, also referred to as actuator, emits an electrical charge that is converted into a mechanical strain by a PZT sensor. We used the *FieldCAL* pulser, which generates burst signals with varying frequencies (30, 60, 150 or 300 kHz). This AE generation demands a good coupling between the PZT sensor and the medium. Due to the 60 kHz resonant frequency of the *R6UG – TC* sensor, the 60 kHz pulse frequency of the *FieldCAL* is the most interesting one.

Pencil lead break (Method 1b)

Pencil lead break enables to simulate an acoustic emission event using

the fracture of a graphite lead. For this, the pencil lead tip with a length of approximately 2–3 mm of a fine-lead mechanical pencil (with 0.5 mm diameter and *HB* lead) is broken by pressing it against the surface of the sample. Similar to a natural AE source, this generates a strong AE signal that is detected as a strong burst by the sensor. The average frequency is estimated to be 50 kHz.

Schmidt-Hammer (Method 1c)

Schmidt-Hammer, also referred to as *rebound hammer*, is a tool for testing the quality of concrete. It generates a repeatable impulse with constant and very high intensity, applied on a rock surface. The frequency is not determined yet.

Coupling sensor with medium (Method 2)

Every time an AE sensor is used, it has to be coupled properly with the medium. The sensor with couplant is pressed gently on the medium and it has to be rotated many times that the unwanted air can move away.

Measuring AE (Method 3)

There are two different possibilities how the signal of the coupled sensor is measured (one for the lab and one for the field).

Laboratory AE measurements (Method 3a)

For all laboratory experiments, the sensors are connected over the *USB AE Node* (if necessary with an amplifier) with the *AEwin* software installed on a netbook.

Field AE measurements (Method 3b)

For the field installation, the two prototypes of the AE-box are used. More details about the AE-boxes are given by Hunziker (2011).

3.2.2 Materials and Media: Determination of Acoustic Characteristics

Amplitude measurements (Method 4)

The measurements of the amplitude are used themselves or enable to calculate the attenuation (Method 5). Different experiment set-ups are used, depending on the scale of the investigated medium. The used method for AE generation (Method 1) depends on the scale. The pulser is used for small and medium scale experiments, while

the pencil lead break method is used for medium or even big scale experiments. For the big scale experiments, which happen in the field, the Schmidt-Hammer is mainly used.

Small scale: mm – cm (*Method 4a*)

There are three different scenarios to measure the amplitude of different media and media-combinations (Figure 3.2). The three scenarios feature different layers with various media between the pulser and sensor. The sequences between pulser and sensor are as follows: *Scenario A* just couplant; *Scenario B* couplant, medium 1, couplant; *Scenario C* couplant, medium 1, medium 2, medium 1, couplant.

Figure 3.2: Method to measure amplitude at small scale: experimental set-up.

Medium scale: cm – dm (*Method 4b*)

The sensor is coupled on the surface of a medium. The AE is generated at a distance of 30 cm either by the pulser or the pencil lead break method (Figure 3.3). In most cases, the pulser is used, because its frequency is known more accurate than the frequency of the pencil lead break.

Big scale: dm – m (*Method 4c*)

The big scale experiments were performed in the field. The sensor is installed at depth in rock using the designed assembly method. Artificial AE sources are generated on the rock surface.

Figure 3.3: Method to measure amplitude at medium scale: experimental set-up.

Attenuation (*Method 5*)

In this thesis, the loss of signal amplitude is investigated. It can be caused by material specific factors (e.g., internal friction; see page 28) as well as factors due to the measurement assembly. There are two different ways to determine the attenuation, either (i) comparison of two amplitudes based on standardized measurements with constant artificial AE sources and one sensor or (ii) comparison of two amplitudes measured with two AE sensors at the same time. For this thesis, the second way is chosen, whereby two different possibilities exist how the measurement set-up can be designed (Figure 3.4):

Absolute attenuation (Method 5a)

One sensor (S_{ref}) is coupled directly with the medium whereby the second sensor (S_{test1}) is coupled with one part of the configuration changed. The artificial AE sources are generated in the perpendicular bisector at varying distances. The attenuation can be calculated by the comparison of the measured amplitudes at the two sensors: $A_{S_{ref}}^{dB} - A_{S_{test1}}^{dB}$.

Comparative attenuation (Method 5b)

Both sensors (S_{test1} and S_{test2}) are coupled with different parts of the configuration changed and the artificial AE sources are generated on the perpendicular bisector at varying distances. The comparative attenuation can be calculated by the comparison of the measured amplitudes at the two sensors: $A_{S_{test1}}^{dB} - A_{S_{test2}}^{dB}$.

Figure 3.4: Method to measure attenuation: experimental set-up.

Attenuation coefficient (*Method 6*)

In this thesis, the linear attenuation coefficient

$$\alpha = \frac{A_0^{\text{dB}} - A^{\text{dB}}}{r} \quad (3.1)$$

(derivation in the Appendix A.1) is determined by a separate experiment. Sensor 1 (S_{test1}) and sensor 2 (S_{test2}) are coupled in a line on the surface of a medium. The artificial AE sources are generated on this line (but not between the sensor; Figure 3.5) using either a pulser or the pencil lead break method. Regarding Equation 3.1, A_0 corresponds to the amplitude of sensor 2, A to the amplitude of sensor 1 and r to the distance d between sensor 1 and 2.

The determined attenuation coefficients have to be interpreted carefully, because its measurement set-up is simple and susceptible to error.

Figure 3.5: Method to measure attenuation coefficient: experimental set-up.

3.2.3 Statistics for Empirical Testing

The experiments should be representative. Hence, each experiment is repeated 10 to 20 times and the average as well as the standard deviation are calculated. The standard deviation represents the uncertainty, if the error of the measurement is unknown. If the error is known and new variables are calculated, the error propagation is determined. Where needed and if possible, systematic errors are considered.

3.2.4 Characterization of Field Site

A short instruction to characterize the field site location is shown here.

Installation parameters (*Characterization 1*)

Exposition (azimuth direction angle), slope, altitude as well as coordinates are determined using a geologic compass and a GPS.

Picture (*Characterization 2*)

Pictures of each location (with and without a rectangle scale) and an overview picture of the whole installation are taken.

Surrounding relief (*Characterization 3*)

Local horizon shading by small features in the rock-wall, especially its facet-structure and micro-topography, can be measured using a calibrated fish-eye camera on a specialized mount to determine the surrounding relief and to follow the incoming radiation (Gruber et al., 2003; Gruber, 2005). This characterization is relevant because topographic shading has a major effect on solar radiation and thus on the rock temperature. Local horizons are recorded using a digital camera (Nikon Coolpix 990) with a fish-eye converter (Nikon FC-E8).

Borehole inside view (*Characterization 4*)

An endoscopic camera, which enables to detect visible cracks, can be used for borehole inside views. The light of the camera has to be very strong, otherwise nothing is visible.

Drill core: Lithology, porosity and density (*Characterization 5*)

The characterization of the drill core enables to discover potential inhomogeneity at depth. At first, the lithology is determined. Afterwards, the porosity of the drill core can be determined as follows (based on Egli et al., 2009):

1. Measure the initial weight of the drill core ($M_{initial}$).
2. Put drill cores in a water pot and generate a vacuum.
3. Measure the weight of the water saturated drill core (M_{wet}).
4. Dry the drill core in an oven (105° C) during 48 hours.
5. Measure weight of dry drill core and determine volume of drill core (M_{dry} ; V_{total}).
6. Calculate the porosity as follows:

$$V_{pores,abs} = \frac{M_{wet} - M_{dry}}{\rho_{water}} \Rightarrow v_{pores,rel} = \frac{V_{pores}}{V_{total}} \quad (3.2)$$

And to the end, the density can be calculated:

$$\rho = M_{initial}/V_{total} \quad (3.3)$$

4 Generic Design of Measurement Assembly

This chapter shows the way from the ideal conception over the procedure of designing and developing to a selection of elaborated measurement assemblies. In the third section, experimental tests and testing criteria are defined.

4.1 Basic Concepts and Possible Solutions

Measuring AE at depth is conceptually easy. Figure 4.1 shows a classical simplified field site with two different AE sources at different depth with their wave propagation. To measure the AE of these two sources and to localize them, sensor 1 is put close to the surface and sensor 2 is put at about 0.5 m depth. Sensor 1 measures both AE sources whereby sensor 2 measures only the lower source, because the spatial range of ultrasonic waves in rock is limited. In reality, this can be complicated because, e.g., retrieving the AE signal from a steep rock-wall at a given depth requires drilling a borehole.

In principle, there are two basic concepts to transmit the AE signal from the point of interest (POI; location where the AE signal should be measured) to the AE sensor:

1 – Use of a waveguide

A waveguide (transmitting pole or bar) can be used to transmit the AE signal from the POI to the rock surface and the sensor. The sensor can be bonded at the upper end of the waveguide with glue or couplant. There are two possibilities how the waveguide can be fixed in the rock close to the POI:

- The waveguide can be glued at the end of the hole.
- The waveguide can be fixed at the end of the hole using an extension anchor.

Figure 4.1: AE sensing in an ideal conception with AE sources at depth.

2 – Direct insertion of the sensor in the borehole

In this case, the sensor is fixed at depth very close to the POI. There are three possibilities how an AE sensor can theoretically be coupled with the rock:

- The sensor can be connected directly with the rock using a couplant to improve the bonding.
- The sensor can be glued directly on the rock.
- The sensor is bonded with a couplant on a transmitting plate, which is glued directly on the rock.

For the desired measurement assembly, the sensor must not be glued directly on the rock, otherwise the sensor is not removable and the Requirement 5 is not fulfilled anymore.

For these methods, it is necessary to drill a hole into the rock to measure AE at depth. The defined requirements lead to elaborate two possible solutions, one for each basic concept (Figure 4.2). The space between the measurement assembly and the borehole wall has to be filled due to two main reasons (Requirement 3): (1) there must not be an artificial water channel along the rod because freezing water causes a high AE activity and (2) the measurement assembly must not touch the wall of the hole, otherwise the signal can be influenced by AE from other depths. Hence, this space has to be filled with a damping and waterproof sealing material. This problem is discussed in Section 5.5 (laboratory Experiment 5).

4.1.1 Measurement Assembly I – Waveguide

A thin rod is either glued or anchored at the bottom of the borehole and the sensor is installed at the rock surface. The used waveguide has to feature good transmitting properties. The waveguide measurement assembly was used by David Amitrano and Stephan Gruber in spring 2010 during a four-day campaign with AE sensing at the rock surface of mountain permafrost. Figure 4.3 shows the construction and installation.

The main uncertainties and challenges using this measurement assembly are described here in more detail:

- The material of a waveguide should transmit the AE signal as good as possible. Hence, seismic velocity and acoustic impedance should

Figure 4.2: Two possible solutions for AE measurement assembly.

be high while attenuation has to be small. Further the material must not corrode when it is used outdoors.

- A main problem of the waveguide is the attenuation. Theoretically, the longer the waveguide is the lower is the measured amplitude at the sensor. This stress wave attenuation due to geometric spreading and internal friction can be calculated with equation 2.16.
- Contact between rock and waveguide is shown in Section 4.1, either you use an extension anchor (Figure 4.3b) or just glue the waveguide in the hole. The problem with the extension anchor might be to get every time the same anchoring effect. Further, to fix the extension anchor exactly at the POI (e.g., at 10 cm depth) is a challenge and you get a big variability of the contact quality. Hence, using an extension anchor, the Requirement 2 can likely not be met. Consequently, it might be preferable to glue the waveguide in the hole.
- To get a fixation without contact with the wall, it is necessary to drill two holes with different diameter (Figure 4.3d) to be able to fix the

(a) Sketch of idea

(b) Picture of waveguide

(c) Picture of installed waveguide

(d) Waveguides fixed at different depth

Figure 4.3: Waveguide measurement assembly. (a) Sketch with an AE sensor on a metal plate, which is fixed at the end of a thread bar. (b) Picture of a waveguide with an extension anchor, using Fixation I. (c) Picture of an installed waveguide in the field, using an extension anchor and Fixation II (from Stephan Gruber, 2010). (d) Sketch of fixed waveguides at different depth with borehole width adjustment.

waveguide at the bottom of the borehole and to fill the gap with a sealing material.

- To have a good connection between the waveguide and the sensor, there is a transmitting plate which is fixed at the end of the waveguide with a flat surface for the sensor (Figure 4.3a). Either with two screws, a small plate and a spring (Fixation I) or an elastic strap (Fixation II), a constant contact pressure can be maintained (Fixation I is used in Figure 4.3b and Fixation II in Figure 4.3c).
- If the sensor is fixed at the end of the waveguide, a protection for the sensor against external influences like water, snow and ice, wind, rock fall and so on is needed.

According to these and other factors, the Requirements 3 and 4 might be difficult to meet. But this installation might be good for lab and field tests at the surface during a short period, but not for outdoor AE monitoring at depth.

4.1.2 Installation Method II – Direct Insertion with Casing

The design of the direct insertion of the sensor in the borehole is a bit more complicated compared to the waveguide. The idea is to insert and fix the sensor in the borehole. The sensor itself is accommodated in a casing, e.g., in a hollow rod. Using a rod, it almost fills the borehole and enables to sustain the access to the sensor. Therefore, it is called *AE-rod*. A sketch of the principal idea is shown in Figure 4.2. Like this, the sensor is installed very close to the POI and can be removed any time.

The resulting uncertainties and challenges are:

- A relevant part of this measurement assembly is the choice of adequate materials. On the one hand, the wave attenuation of the transmitting plate should be very small to minimize the signal loss. On the other hand, the wave attenuation of the rod itself and the sealing material should have a bigger wave attenuation than the surrounding rock, so that AE do not propagate easier through the installation to the sensor than through the rock. Further, the rod has to be mechanically robust and waterproof.

- There is no direct contact between sensor and rock. As described in Section 4.1, a thin transmitting plate, which is fixed in this case at the end of the rod, is glued in the borehole. The AE sensor is bonded on the top site of this plate with couplant. Like this, the AE sensor is fixed very close to the POI and can be removed from the transmitting plate without damage (Requirement 5). But what kind of transmission medium can be used?
- The sensor *R6UG-TC* with the axial cable connection has a BNC connector with a diameter of 15 mm, whereby the diameter of the cable is only 3 mm. Because this cable must not be cut, a custom waterproof lid is needed. It should allow to open the lid and to remove or exchange the sensor.

4.2 Problem Definition: Tests and Criteria

In the previous sections, various challenges and uncertainties of the two measurement assemblies are raised. To investigate and clarify them, this section defines the experimental tests as well as their criteria.

4.2.1 Design Experiments

First, laboratory experiments should help to select best-suited materials as well as to extend and improve the in-depth knowledge. Hence, the following questions and uncertainties have to be investigated:

1 – Contact between measurement assembly and sensor

Experimental test: (a) Which couplants are suitable for this kind of use (e.g., long term, big temperature range, ultrasonic wave)?
(b) What happens if the couplant freezes?

Testing criterion: (a) Test a range of different couplants and check with which one a good coupling with a low wave attenuation over the long term results. (b) The couplant itself should not cause any AE during freezing.

2 – Components of measurement assemblies

Experimental test: Which materials are ideal for the AE measurement assemblies? Which materials should be avoided?

Testing criterion: On the one hand, the coupling part has to feature low and temperature-independent wave attenuation. On the other hand, the other parts (e.g., the rod of the AE-rod measurement assembly) have to feature bigger wave attenuation than the rock itself.

3 – Contact between rock and measurement assembly

Experimental test: (a) Which glue is optimal? (b) Is there a difference between glued thread bar and extending anchor?

Testing criterion: (a) The glue has to stick on rock as well as on metal and has to be well manageable (in an approximate temperature range $-10^{\circ}\text{C} < T < 50^{\circ}\text{C}$). (b) The contact has to be constant, reliable and repeatable.

4 – Waveguide vs. AE-rod: Loss of AE

Experimental test: (a) Which measurement assembly shows the lowest wave attenuation? (b) What is the influence of the length of the waveguide?

Testing criterion: (a) The measurement assembly should have a weak damping of the AE signal. (b) If the waveguide measurement assembly features the lower attenuation in (a), the influence of its length has to be negligible.

5 – Sealing the AE-rod

Experimental test: (a) Which materials are available to seal a 5 mm space with 0.5 m length? (b) Which ones can be used at an approximate temperature range $-10^{\circ}\text{C} < T < 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ and how are they used (filling procedure)?

Testing criterion: (a) Material which can be filled in such a small space and which does not fill all cracks and fissures in the rock. This is a trade-off between viscosity, surface tension and pot life. (b) The physical properties like viscosity or pot life must not change too fast or have to be adapted, that such a small space can still be filled.

6 – Interaction AE source - PZT sensor

Experimental test: What is the influence of the incidence angle? Does the orientation of the sensor matter?

Testing criterion: This experimental test helps to extend the knowledge of AE measurements.

The description, results and discussion of these necessary experiments are shown in Chapter 5.

4.2.2 Characterization and Validation Experiments

As soon as a prototype of the designed measurement assembly is built, it has to be characterized and validated.

Lab – Prototype in freezer

Experimental test: (a) Are there AE during cooling due to the AE-rod itself? (b) Are there AE during warming due to the AE-rod itself? (a)+(b) If yes, at which temperature or temperature gradient does it happen?

Testing criterion: (a)+(b) The AE activity of the AE-rod sensor should not be higher than the reference sensor.

Field – Artificial pulses with installed measurement assembly

Experimental test: Which AE frequency is detectable in the field and how big is the spatial range?

Testing criterion: There is no explicit criterion, but this experiment helps to characterize the installed measurement assembly.

The exact description, results and discussion of these necessary experiments are shown in Chapter 6.

5 Design Experiments

The two measurement assemblies *waveguide* and *AE-rod* are tested and compared in this chapter using different experiments and analyses. The results are used either to extend the knowledge about AE in rock, to support the design phase, to improve the principal ideas or to confirm the different testing criteria. The synthesis of these results should lead to a final design in Chapter 6.

The six main parts defined in Section 4.2.1 are covered and discussed in this chapter. Each of these laboratory experiments is usually structured in the three paragraphs: *A – Rationale and Description*, *B – Results and Analysis* and *C – Discussion and Conclusion*.

5.1 Contact between Measurement Assembly and Sensor: Couplants

A – Rationale and Description

The couplant is a substance that is placed between the AE sensor and the medium. Its purpose is to avoid that air (which has a low wave velocity) can stay between the AE sensor and the medium and to transmit the AE waves with a small attenuation. Many different products exist.

In this experiment, a selection of couplants are investigated. The couplants must not cause AE during freezing and thawing themselves, should not show any deformation but should transmit the AE signal with as little loss as possible.

At first, qualitative factors such as characteristics, handling and practicality were checked and tested. Couplants with suitable qualitative factors were tested further: On the one hand, if they cause AE themselves in the freezer. On the other hand, amplitude measurements (Method 4a) by face to face coupling of the pulser (*FieldCAL*) with the sensor showed the differences between the tested couplants.

B – Results and Analysis

Table 5.1 gives an overview of the investigated couplants and Figure 5.1 shows the results of the measured amplitudes using the different couplants.

C – Discussion and Conclusion

The results show that there are several suitable couplants. Concerning the wave attenuation by the couplant, Figure 5.1 shows that the couplant *UCA-2* and *F* of *Sofranel* might be the best of the tested couplants. A simple removal of the sensor from a medium after using couplant might be prevented due to the vacuum effect. Hence, the sensor has to be tilted to overcome the contact pressure due to the vacuum. The removal of the sensor is possible with both *Sofranel* couplant (*UCA-2* and *F*). For this thesis, the couplant *UCA-2* is used for all experiments and installations. The decision is based on the PMUC accreditation of *UCA-2* that is an addition indication of high quality and the fact that the ideal temperature range of couplant *F* according to the manufacturer is between +50° C and +280° C.

5.2 Components of Measurement Assembly

A – Rationale and Description

The designed measurement assemblies are composed of several components with different materials. As transmitting candidate materials, which should have a low impedance and a small attenuation coefficient, ordinary mild steel, chromium steel (Ni-Cr-steel) and aluminum were chosen. For the damping material, which should have low transmission coefficient and large attenuation, POM C (a popular trade name is Dupont Delrin®) was selected. The following sub-experiments and calculations helped to investigate the characteristics of the different candidate materials.

I Amplitude

For the three transmitting candidates, the potential damping material and gneiss, the absolute amplitude for different pulser frequencies was measured using Method 4a.

Table 5.1: Overview of tested couplants.

Couplant	Manufacturer	Description & Characteristics	Handling & Practicability	Generate AE
A	Sofranel	Liquid; PMUC ^a ; $T < +50^{\circ}\text{C}$	Suboptimal due to liquidity	— ^b
B	Sofranel	Liquid; PMUC ^a ; $T < +50^{\circ}\text{C}$	Suboptimal due to liquidity	— ^b
C	Sofranel	Liquid; $T < 120^{\circ}\text{C}$	Suboptimal due to liquidity	— ^b
UCA-2	Sofranel	Thixotropic gel; high viscosity; PMUC ^a , inspect big surfaces, vertical walls & ceiling	Easy handling and application	no
F	Sofranel	Grease; $+50^{\circ}\text{C} < T < +280^{\circ}\text{C}$	Easy handling and application	no
Silicones	Wacker	High-vacuum grease; medium duty	Easy handling and application	no
glisseal HV	borer chemie	Grease for laboratories; high vacuum quality; $-40^{\circ}\text{C} < T < +320^{\circ}\text{C}$	Easy handling and application	no

^a Produits et matériaux utilisables en centrales (accreditation for products and materials used in power plants)

^b Not tested due to the unsuitable handling

Figure 5.1: Result of Experiment 1: Measured amplitude at the sensor with four different pulser frequencies (*FieldCAL*) using the different couplants, including error bars.

II Calculation of C_1 , Z and T

The speed of sound C_1 , the acoustic impedance Z_1 and the transmission coefficient T regarding gneiss were calculated for mild steel, aluminum, Ni-Cr-steel and POM C.

III Estimation of attenuation coefficient α

Using Method 6, the linear attenuation coefficient α was determined for mild steel, aluminum, Ni-Cr-steel and POM C.

B – Results and Analysis

Figure 5.2 summarizes the result of Sub-experiment I. The results of Sub-experiment II and III are given in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Result of Sub-experiment 2-II and 2-III: Properties of material candidates.

<i>Material</i>	<i>Speed of sound C_1 [m/s]</i>	<i>Acoustic impedance Z_1 [SI]^a</i>	<i>Transmission coefficient T^b</i>	<i>Attenuation coefficient α [dB/m]</i>
Mild steel	5838	$46.1 \cdot 10^6$	0.71	30
Aluminum	6451	$17.4 \cdot 10^6$	0.99	10
Ni-Cr-steel	5838	$46.1 \cdot 10^6$	0.71	60
POM C	1841	$2.61 \cdot 10^6$	0.53	71

^a SI unit of acoustic impedance: $\text{kg}/(\text{s} \cdot \text{m}^2)$

^b Compared to gneiss

C – Discussion and Conclusion

The properties of the measurement assembly's components are relevant for the quality of the measurements. Figure 5.2 shows the measured amplitude at the different materials. It is visible that the amplitude for aluminum, mild steel and chromium steel are in the same range. Depending on the pulse frequency the order can change a bit. Compared to the literature (Table 2.5), the calculated speed of sound and acoustic impedance of the different material candidates are basically a bit higher. Concerning the transmission and attenuation coefficients, aluminum shows the best values, but the steel ones are still acceptable whereof Ni-Cr-steels has a very high attenuation

Figure 5.2: Result of Sub-experiment 2-I: Amplitude at the sensor with four different pulser frequencies (*FieldCAL*), including error bars.

coefficient. Another relevant factor is the machining of the metals whereof aluminum and mild steel are much easier than Ni-Cr-steel, but mild steel corrodes. Therefore, for the metal plate of the AE-rod, aluminum is used. Because there are no extension bolts that are made of aluminum, mild steel is used for the waveguide.

5.3 Contact Between Rock and Measurement Assembly

A – Rationale and Description

The contact between rock and sensor is an essential part of all different installation methods for suitable and reliable data sensing. There are two sub-experiments:

I Glue

The glue has to bond the measurement assembly to the rock. There are several glues commercially available whereof a selection was tested. The first testing criteria were whether they stick on stone and on metal at room temperature (approximately +25° C) as well as in the freezer (approximately –10° C). When a glue stuck properly and the handling was suitable, in a second step the wave attenuation caused by the glue was determined based on amplitude measurements. For this, Method 4a was used, where medium 1 corresponded to an aluminum plate (4 mm thickness, 30 mm diameter) and medium 2 to the tested glues. The sticking and handling factors are qualitative factors whereas wave attenuation is a quantitative one. This sub-experiment enables to determine the influence of the aluminum plate and the glue by amplitude measurements and attenuation calculations.

II Glued thread bar vs. extension anchor

In this sub-experiment, the two simple ways how a waveguide can be fixed (compare Section 4.1 and 4.1.1) were tested and compared. The first waveguide (*WG1*; mild steel thread bar; 10 mm diameter; 85 mm length) was glued in a 5 cm deep borehole and the second one (galvanized steel extension anchor; 10 mm diameter; 85 mm length) was fixed in a 5 cm deep borehole. Method 5a was used to determine the attenuation due to the waveguide fixation. To generate an artifi-

cial AE, the pencil lead breaking method was applied (Method 1b). Figure 5.3 shows the experimental set-up.

Figure 5.3: Set-up of Experiment 3: Two different rock-sensor contacts.

B – Results and Analysis

Table 5.3 gives an overview of the tested glues of Sub-experiment I. Figure 5.4 shows the results of the measured amplitude for the Scenario A, B and C of Method 4a. Figure 5.5 shows the result of Sub-experiment II.

C – Discussion and Conclusion

The results of Sub-experiment I show that either *2K Standard (forbo)* or *Standard Araldit* can be used for the installation. All other glues either do not stick on rock or metal at different temperatures or the handling is unsuitable for field installation. Regarding the loss of signal amplitude due to the glue, the values are very similar. Because of the handling factor, the *2K Standard (forbo)* is used for the further laboratory and field experiments or installation.

The results of Sub-experiment II show that there is a clear difference between the two waveguide installation methods. The contact between rock and waveguide is much better if you glue a thread bar into the borehole instead of using an extension anchor. Further, using an extension anchor, it is difficult to repeat the installation reliably because the extending and binding are not equally effective every time and depend on the rock quality.

Table 5.3: Overview of tested glues.

Name	Glue		Description	Adhesive bonding on ^a		Handling
	Manufacturer			Rock	Metal	
Alleskleber	forbo		Transparent	bad	bad	good
Metall-/ Kontaktkleber	forbo		Heat-resistant up to 100° C	bad	so-so	good
Kontaktkleber	forbo		Universal	bad	bad	good
TIM V+300	TILCA		Two component adhesive	good	bad	very good
2K-Standard	forbo		Epoxy adhesive; drying time 30 min	good	good	very good
2K-Metall	forbo		Epoxy adhesive; drying time 5 min	bad	good	very good
Araldit Rapid	Araldit		Epoxy adhesive; fast-setting (5 min); multifunctional applicable	so-so	so-so	good
Araldit Standard	Araldit		Epoxy adhesive; slow-setting (90 min); high resistance	good	good	good
RESIDUR VP 349	Kümpel AG		PU	good	good	too liquid
RESIDUR VP 701	Kümpel AG		PU	good	good	too liquid

^a Glued at room temperature (approximately +25° C) and in freezer (approximately -10° C)

Figure 5.4: Result of Sub-experiment 3-I: Amplitude at the sensor with four different pulser frequencies (*FieldCAL*) for the different scenarios including error bars.

Figure 5.5: Result of Sub-experiment 3-II: Wave attenuation due to thread bar fixed with glue (*WG1*) and due to extension anchor (*WG2*) compared to the reference sensor, including error bars.

5.4 Waveguide vs. AE-rod: Wave Attenuation of AE

A – Rationale and Description

The following experiments compare the two rock-sensor contacts of waveguide and AE-rod and check which one shows the lower wave attenuation. For this purpose, the absolute attenuation was determined with method 5a using a gneiss rock sample ($70 \times 15 \times 10$ cm). To generate an artificial AE, the pencil lead breaking method was applied (Method 1b). The two waveguides *WG3* (mild steel thread bar; 10 mm diameter; 120 mm length) and *WG4* (mild steel threadbar; 10 mm diameter; 420 mm length) were glued in a 2.5 cm deep borehole, while the metal plate of the AE-rod (*MP2*; aluminum, 4 mm thickness, 30 mm diameter) is glued on the surface of the rock. As reference, a metal plate (*MP1*; aluminum, 4 mm thickness, 30 mm diameter) was coupled directly on the rock surface using *UCA-2* couplant.

B – Results and Analysis

Table 5.4 summarizes the absolute attenuation of the rock-sensor contact.

Table 5.4: Result of Experiment 4: Absolute attenuation measured for different rock-sensor contacts.

	<i>Mean attenuation (dB)</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>
MP1	1.1	0.3
MP2	1.9	0.7
WG3	10.0	1.1
WG4	9.7	1.3

C – Discussion and Conclusion

The result shows clearly that the waveguide causes a much bigger wave attenuation than the AE-rod. This can be seen for the short (*WG3*) as well as for the long waveguide (*WG4*). An interesting observation is, that the longer waveguide does not cause a bigger wave attenuation than the short one.

5.5 Sealing

A – Rationale and Description

The space between the AE-rod or the waveguide and the borehole wall (Figure 6.1c and 4.3d) has to be filled with a material, which prevents water flow in the hole and damps the propagation of AE waves from the rock to the POM tube or to the sensor. There are several requirements for the filling material:

1. Lower acoustic impedance and smaller heat conductivity than rock, elastic, waterproof and temperature resistant (-20° to $+30^{\circ}$ C)
2. The viscosity, surface tension and pot life of the filling material have to be such, that a gap with a width of 4.6 mm can be filled up to 50 cm depth, but the fissures in the rock should not get filled.
3. The filling material has to be workable and has to desiccate in harsh environments with sub-zero temperatures (processing temperature approximately -10° to $+25^{\circ}$ C).

The speed of sound C_1 , the acoustic impedance Z_1 and the transmission coefficient T regarding gneiss were calculated for the resulting filling material. Further, the linear attenuation coefficient α was determined, using Method 6.

B – Results and Analysis

The best solution found is a custom product called *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* from Kümpel AG. It meets all defined requirements. The *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* features the following technical properties (personal communication Mr. Roland Deutsch, Kümpel AG, June 30, 2011):

- *Processing time:* 30 - 35 minutes at room temperature and 2 h at 0° C
- *Mixing ratio:* resin : hardener = 10 : 3
- *Density:* resin = 1.016 g/cm^3 , hardener = 1.027 g/cm^3
- *Mixture viscosity:* 850 mPas (i.e. between olive oil and liquid honey)

5 Design Experiments

The acoustic characteristics C_1 , Z , T as well as the linear attenuation coefficient α are shown in Table 5.5.

A big disadvantage of the *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* is, that its properties are changing if it is mixed with water while it is liquid. Already the ratio 9 : 1 between *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* and water changes the processing time and the product remains sticky for undefined time. Figure 5.6 shows different mixture ratios.

Figure 5.6: Pictures of different mixture ratios between *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* and water.

Table 5.5: Result of Sub-experiment 5-II and 5-III: Properties of the filling material.

Material	Speed of sound C_1 [m/s]	Acoustic impedance Z [SI]	Transmission coefficient T	Attenuation coefficient α [dB/m]
RESIDUR Geo-Gel	610	$0.62 \cdot 10^6$	0.16	151

C – Discussion and Conclusion

Several products have been considered, but *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* is the only one which meets all requirements. For example normal silicon has a too high viscosity and *SilGel* (WACKER SilGel® is a highly transparent silicone rubber compound that cure to form silicone gels) does not cure at subzero temperatures. The *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* can be filled in a small gap with 4 mm width up to 1 m depth using a cartridge and a long thin metal tube (Figure 5.7).

The problem of the mixture between *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* and water can be solved when drying the boreholes properly before sealing and covering them afterwards until cured.

5.6 Interaction AE Source – PZT Sensor

There are many factors that influence the generation and propagation of acoustic waves (Section 2.3.3). Due to the AE-rod, the interaction between AE source and AE sensor might have special characteristics and dimensions.

Initially, in this experiment the factors *distance between AE source and AE-rod*, *intensity of AE source* and *incidence at AE-rod or AE sensor* were planned to be varied and investigated to get an idea how much the signal is influenced by them. But due to anisotropy of the stone samples no useful results can be presented in this thesis and due to lack of time no further experiments with other samples have been done yet. Already Goueygou et al. (2003) highlighted the difficulty of obtaining accurate estimates of ultrasonic parameters due to the high variability of the materials (e.g., stone samples) under study.

Figure 5.7: Filling procedure for sealing: The use of a cartridge and a long thin metal tube enables to fill the *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* in a small gap with 4 mm width up to 1 m. To test and practice the filling procedure, two acrylic glass tubes (with different diameters that the space between them is exactly 4 mm) were used.

6 Synthesis, Field Installation and First Results

This chapter shows the synthesis of the design phase and experimental tests on the final assembly, and presents the final measurement assembly. Furthermore, the field installation of the first measurement assemblies is described and first results are shown.

6.1 Synthesis to Final Measurement Assembly

6.1.1 Waveguide vs. AE-Rod

Most results of the laboratory experiments have already been discussed in the previous chapter. This section gives a synthesis of the most relevant results.

Material properties

For the different potential materials, transmitting and damping media, the speed of sound, acoustic impedance, transmission coefficient and the attenuation coefficient were determined. Table 6.1 gives an overview of the material properties. These calculations base on the assumption of isotropic and homogeneous elasticity of the investigated media, an assumption that may be an over-simplification for some materials (e.g., gneiss shows a high anisotropic structure). Further, the uncertainty of the attenuation coefficient is up to 5 dB/m. Hence, these results have to be interpreted carefully.

The decision to use POM C as transmitting medium is already explained in Experiment 2. It is used for the tube of the AE-rod because its thermal conductivity is an order of magnitude smaller than gneiss and speed of sound, acoustic impedance as well as transmission coefficient are low. POM is a highly-viscous resin, which shows outstanding physical properties, especially toughness, high strength and rigidity in a wide temperature range as well as excellent resistance to moisture (DUPONT, 2011, access: 10/10/2011).

Table 6.1: Material properties.

<i>Material</i>	<i>Speed of sound</i> C_1 [m/s]	<i>Acoustic impedance</i> Z [SI] ^a	<i>Transmission coefficient</i> T ^b	<i>Attenuation coefficient</i> α [dB/m]
Mild steel	5838	$46.1 \cdot 10^6$	0.71	30
Aluminum	6451	$17.4 \cdot 10^6$	0.99	10
Ni-Cr-steel	5838	$46.1 \cdot 10^6$	0.71	60
POM C	1841	$2.61 \cdot 10^6$	0.53	71
RESIDUR Geo-Gel	610	$0.62 \cdot 10^6$	0.16	151
Gneiss	5149	$13.9 \cdot 10^6$	1	35

^a SI unit of acoustic impedance: $\text{kg}/(\text{sm}^2)$

^b Compared to gneiss

RESIDUR Geo-Gel shows much lower speed of sound and acoustic impedance but a much higher attenuation coefficient compared to gneiss. This means that the AE signal propagates much better through gneiss than through *RESIDUR Geo-Gel*. Therefore, this filling material does not falsify the AE measurements but meets the requirements.

Rock-sensor contact

Table 6.2 gives an overview of the six tested rock-sensor contacts. The *MP1* contact shows, that the attenuation due to the 4 mm thick aluminum plate of the AE-rod is approximately 1 dB. If it is glued with the *2K Standard (forbo)* on the rock surface (*MP2*), the total wave attenuation is approximately 2 dB. The results of *WG1* to *WG4* show, that the waveguides cause a bigger attenuation. The difference between the glued and anchored waveguide (*WG1* vs. *WG2*) and the influence of the waveguide length (*WG3* vs. *WG4*) have already been explained in Experiment 3. Comparing the area/sector of the borehole, where the waveguides make contact with the rock, *WG1* (glued WG with 5 cm long contact sector) with *WG3/WG4* (glued WGs with 2.5 cm long contact sector), it is visible that the fixation with the longer contact sector provides a smaller wave attenuation, even if the absolute length of *WG1* is shorter than *WG3/WG4*. In

general, Sikorska & Pan (2004) showed that «dispersion, attenuation, mode conversion and/or waveguide reflections occurring within the waveguide will affect the signals being detected by the sensor» and Ono & Cho (2004) concluded that «Wave propagation in tubes (or hollow cylinders) has a higher level of complexity due to the presence of inner surfaces».

Table 6.2: Attenuation measured for different rock-sensor contacts.

	<i>Mean attenuation (dB)</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>
MP1	1.1	0.3
MP2	1.9	0.7
WG1	2.7	0.8
WG2	8.3	1.8
WG3	10.0	1.1
WG4	9.7	1.3

Regarding the requirements defined in Section 1.4, Table 6.3 shows which requirement is met by which measurement assembly. Requirement 3 *minimal alteration of the site measured* is discussed in Section 6.2, whereby both measurement assemblies can meet this requirement only partly.

Table 6.3: Which measurement assembly meets which requirement.

<i>Requirement</i>	<i>Waveguide</i>	<i>AE-rod</i>
1 – Generation of reliable, consistent and repeatable AE data	partial	yes
2 – Constant coupling between rock and sensor	partial	yes
3 – Minimal alteration of the site measured	partial	partial
4 – Protection of installation	no	yes
5 – Simple assembly and disassembly of the sensor	yes	yes

If you compare the two designed measurement assemblies, there are different advantages and disadvantages. On the one hand, the installation of the measurement assembly and the exchange of the sensor is easier with the waveguide and its production costs are lower. On the other hand, using the AE-rod the sensor is protected, there is a lower wave attenuation and a constant coupling. Both measurement assemblies have the problem of generating an artificial water channel. The sealing does not have an influence on the data quality using an AE-rod, whereas its influence on the transmission of the AE signal through the waveguide is unknown (e.g., damping of the AE signal).

6.1.2 Final Measurement Assembly: AE-Rod

Based on the *design* and *synthesis* steps (Chapters 4 and 5 as well as the previous section), the final measurement assembly (AE-rod), is presented now.

Figure 6.1a+b show sketches of the designed AE-rod. The diameter is 30.8 mm and the length is variable (> 15 cm). Detailed technical drawings are in the Appendix A.2. Inside the casing, the AE sensor is fixed side-wise with an O-ring to prevent a lateral movement and it is pushed on the transmitting plate by a spring to provide a constant contact pressure. The following list gives an overview of the used materials:

- The lid is made of brass and aluminum due to the easier workability. Rubber disks are used to make it waterproof.
- The tube is made of POM C.
- The metal plate is made of a 4 mm thick aluminum plate.

A few prototypes were built for further investigation, especially for characterization in the lab and field. To get a first characterization of the AE-rod, it was put inside a freezer during a temperature cycle (Section 6.1.3).

(a) Side view (drawn by Reto Maier)

(b) Cross section (drawn by Reto Maier)

(c) Installed AE-rod

Figure 6.1: AE-rod: Sketches of the principal idea.

6.1.3 Characterization of AE-Rod: Prototype in Freezer

A – Rationale and Description

The AE-rod is made of several components, which might generate AE themselves during freezing or thawing and consequently deteriorate the measured AE.

Hence, the whole AE-rod underwent a freezing and thawing cycle. The test preparation is shown in Figure 6.2. There is a second sensor in the freezer as a reference for external AE.

Figure 6.2: Sketch of test set-up of «Prototype of AE-rod in freezer».

B – Results and Analysis

Figure 6.3 shows the AE activity of the AE-rod (blue crosses) and a reference sensor (blue dots) as well as the temporal temperature change.

C – Discussion and Conclusion

The results are difficult to interpret as the experimental set-up is rather crude, it is likely that a fraction of the measured events were generated by the freezer, and the experiment was repeated only twice. Hence, for further investigations, experiments with several freezing-thawing cycles in a special cooling chamber would have to be done. But looking at the AE activity (Figure 6.3), it is obviously visible that the AE-rod and the reference AE sensor measure a raised AE activity during the cooling phase, whereby the captured AE activity at the AE-rod is a bit less than at the reference AE sensor. During the warming phase, the AE-rod measures single events, but much fewer than during the cooling phase. The reduced activity measured

6.1 Synthesis to Final Measurement Assembly

Figure 6.3: Results of Experiment 6: AE-rod in cooling chamber. AE activity of AE-rod (blue crosses) itself during temperature change. As reference, a second sensor was put in the cooling chamber (blue dots).

at the AE-rod could be explained by the insulating effect of the AE-rod and thus the damping of the temperature change at the sensor.

6.2 Field Installation

The field installation of prototypes enables to characterize the AE-rod under natural conditions and to investigate *in situ* rock damage driven by freezing. Appendix B presents the *Practical recommendation* that contains a short guidance with the needed steps to reproduce such a measurement set-up by others.

6.2.1 Field Site

This study area on Jungfrauoch is located on the south side below the Sphinx Observatory (Figure 6.4). The Jungfrauoch site is accessible by the *Jungfrauoch railway* all year long.

Figure 6.4: Study area on Jungfrauoch.

Two complete measurement set-ups were installed at two close locations on the Jungfrauoch in a steep rock-wall (Figure 6.5a), named as *top site* (Figure 6.5b) and *bottom site* (Figure 6.5c). The *top site* is on a rather dry

spur-like feature, while the *bottom site* is in a gully-like depression that collects melt-water from the surrounding snow patches. The field installation settings are discussed in Section 6.2.2. Table 6.4 gives a short overview of the relevant characterization for the two locations *top site* and *bottom site*.

Table 6.4: Characterization of the two field sites.

	<i>Top Site</i>	<i>Bottom Site</i>
<i>Altitude</i>	approx. 3530 m a.s.l.	approx. 3525 m a.s.l.
<i>Exposition</i>	$115^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ N	$125^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ N
<i>Slope</i>	$55^\circ \pm 5^\circ$	$40^\circ \pm 5^\circ$
<i>Geology</i>	Cristalline basement «Altkristallin» at high metamorphic grade	
<i>Lithology</i>	Gneiss rich in feldspar	
<i>Rock porosity & density</i>	Depth profiles of the drilling cores are shown in Appendix A.3	

6.2.2 Field Installation Settings

A complete field installation set-up consists of two AE-rods to capture AE at depth and two probes for measuring temperature (*Th3 Soil Temperature Profile Probe*) and relative moisture by capacitance (*Sentek EnviroSMART*) at depth. Due to the spatial range of ultrasonic waves in rock, AE are measured at 10 cm (AE1) and 50 cm (AE2) depth. Having only two AE sensors, it is difficult to get an accurate localization of the source depth, but they can at least provide a depth zonation. An installation of more than two sensors would improve and facilitate the source depth localization whereas it would considerably increase disturbance of the rock. To minimize the alteration of the site measured and to reduce the disturbance caused by the boreholes in the rock closest to the AE sensors, the boreholes were drilled at differing angles with a final alignment of the sensors normal to the rock surface. To prevent an artificial water flow in the borehole, the spaces between the rock and the probes (AE-rod and *Sentek EnviroSMART*) are sealed. Figure 6.6 shows an overview of all installed sensors at one location (the installation adjustment of the two AE sensors is shown in the Appendix A.2). The depth of the *Th3* and *Sentek* probes are not exactly the same for the two different locations, due to difficulties during the drilling campaign.

(a) Overview of *top* and *bottom site* next to the research station;
the length of the yellow tube is approximately 8 m

(b) *Top site*

(c) *Bottom site*

Figure 6.5: The two field sites on Jungfraujoch.

Table 6.5 gives an overview of the sensor depth of the installed probes for the two different locations. Additionally, a webcam to document surface conditions is installed.

Table 6.5: Real sensor depth of the different probes below rock surface.

<i>Probe</i>	<i>Top Site</i>	<i>Bottom Site</i>
<i>AE-rod</i>	10 and 50 cm	10 and 50 cm
<i>Th3</i>	3, 8, 18, 28, 48 and 98 cm	5, 10, 20, 30, 50 and 100 cm
<i>Sentek</i>	10, 20, 30, 50 and 100 cm	10, 20 and 50 cm

6.2.3 Characterization of Installed AE-Rod

The characterization of installed AE-rods is the final experiment, which allows to evaluate the designed measurement assembly under real conditions as well as to show up limits, strengths and weaknesses of it. It is a long term experiment and started in September 2011. Artificial AE are generated on the surface with the pulser (Method 1a), the pencil lead break (Method 1b) and the Schmidt-Hammer (Method 1c) several times under different rock conditions with a given distance from the sensors. Rock condition refers to e.g., different temperatures and temperature gradients as well as different humidity and snow cover. First analysis showed that the generated AEs with Method 1a and Method 1b were too weak and thus no AE were recorded at the installed sensors. Using the Method 1c, there is a big uncertainty and variance of the acquired AE data, maybe due to the low frequency of the Schmidt-Hammer, which is not close to the sensor's resonant frequency. Hence, the analysis is difficult but it provides first experiences, which are going to be improved.

6.3 First Results

This section presents first results of the acquired data. No capacity data are shown, because the probe did not work properly due to technical problems. Figure 6.7 shows the temperature at different depths for the *top* and *bottom site* during the time period from September 11 to October 9, 2011.

(a) 2D-sketch

(b) 3D-sketch

Figure 6.6: Overview of the installed sensors at one location.

Concerning the AE data, only very low AE activities have been recorded at both sensors for the *top site* and at the deeper sensor for the *bottom site*. Unfortunately, the AE-box of the *bottom site* is out of order since October 8, 2011 at 3:29 GMT. Hence, only AE data of the sensor close to the surface for the time period from September 11, 2011, to October 8, 2011, of the *bottom site* are presented (Figure 6.8). Compared to the entire measuring period, there are two periods with a high event rate, amplitude, count and energy (September 19/20 and October 6/7, 2011). An interesting observation is that the amplitude, count and energy are still quite high even when the event rate is low. Figure 6.9 shows the combination of the AE amplitudes at 10 cm depth with temperatures and temperature gradients at different depths for the time period from September 17 to September 23, 2011, of the *bottom site*. High amplitudes of AE are measured as soon as the rock temperature goes below the zero degree level, presumptive due to frost weathering. A direct comparison with the results of the laboratory experiments or even with the results of the four-day experiment in spring 2011 on Jungfrauoch (cf. Amitrano et al., 2011) is difficult. On the one hand, because there were different conditions like rock temperature and temperature gradients. On the other hand, because the AE parameters depend on the used measurement set-up and its setting (e.g., threshold level of AE) and thus are not directly comparable between different systems.

Newest data allow to give an enhanced characterization of the AE-rod compared to the freezer experiment. The investigation of the AE activity in nights with a freezing/thawing cycle over 24 hours features the following insight: (1) At the *top site*, which is very dry, the shorter AE-rod captured only 2 AE events ($count_{event1} = 0$, $count_{event2} = 0$, $A_{event1} = 41.2$ dB, $A_{event2} = 41.3$ dB, $E_{event1} = 7.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$, $E_{event2} = 0.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$) during a whole freezing/thawing cycle (October 20/21, 2011) with a temperature range from -3.4° C to 15.7° C at 5 cm depth and -4.4° C to 11.7° C at 10 cm depth; (2) At the *bottom site*, which has a lot of available water, the AE-rod captured a lot of AE events with much higher counts, amplitude and energy during a similar temperature cycle (e.g., October 7, 2011; cf. Figure 6.7 and 6.8). Therefore, the AE-rod itself does not cause any considerable AE events even if it get cooled down to minus temperatures.

These first results are a strong evidence, that the designed measurement assembly enables to successfully capture AE events in the field.

(a) *Top site*

(b) *Bottom site*

Figure 6.7: Temperature at different depths for the two locations (using GMT).

Figure 6.8: AE activity at 10 cm depth for *bottom site* (using GMT). The threshold was lowered from 50 dB to 40 dB on September 21.

Figure 6.9: AE amplitude at 10 cm depth and temperature as well as temperature gradients for *bottom site* (using GMT). The threshold was lowered from 50 dB to 40 dB on September 21.

7 Conclusion

This thesis describes the design and testing of a suitable measurement assembly for outdoor acoustic sensing. Based on defined requirements, two basic concepts to capture AE signals were developed: either the AE signal is transmitted to the surface where it is measured or it is measured directly at depth. This led to the two possible solutions using a waveguide or inserting the sensor directly into the borehole within a casing. The performed experiments favored a construction based on the direct insertion with casing, namely the AE-rod. Four prototypes of this final measurement assembly are installed at two different depths on the Jungfraujoeh at two neighboring locations. To measure the main controlling factors, temperature and capacity probes are installed at both locations. These two locations now acquire AE, temperature and moisture data, which will enable to investigate the processes associated with rock fracturing as well as temporal changes of water and ice content under real conditions. This is work in progress that will lead to better process understanding. Further, the combination of an AE monitoring network with a temperature model might help to discern sensitive zones and times for cryogenic fracturing.

The design and testing of the AE-rod feature strengths, weaknesses and limits. The AE-rod causes an attenuation of only approximately 2 dB, is very robust, can be installed anywhere and at the desired depth, but the field installation is complex, time-consuming and expensive. Already the casing (without sensor) of the AE-rod costs more than an AE sensor. All this could be simplified if the sensors were glued directly in the borehole. Maybe even the attenuation would be lower, but using this simplified assembly, the AE sensor cannot be exchanged or retrieved from the borehole and thus does not meet an initially defined requirement. The following itemization might sound negative or even pessimistic, but it should only mark assumptions and simplifications for the experiments.

- Only the AE parameter amplitude and its loss are compared and used for calculations. But there would be other interesting parameters like duration, rise time, count or energy.

- The coupling of the sensor with a medium is very difficult. Even with rotating, the repetition of the coupling at the same place can already generate a variation of 2 – 3 dB (personal communication Mr. Manuel Löhr, Physical Acoustic, August 23, 2011). However, personal experiences have shown an uncertainty of approximately 1 dB.
- The artificial AE source and the AE sensor were attached in the lab experiments on the same surface of the sample, but under real conditions the AE source is in the interior and the waves propagate spherically.
- The determination of the material properties is an estimation and features considerable uncertainties, but a direct comparison of the different material candidates was still possible.
- The glue thickness can vary and its influence on the attenuation was not investigated.
- The P- and S-waves of the AE signal are not distinguished, but the acoustic impedances and the transmission coefficients were calculated based on the speed of sound of the P-waves.
- The same kind of stone sample (high metamorphic gneiss from Ticino, Switzerland, without any cracks, flat surfaces and limited sizes) was used in all experiments. The results using a gneiss stone sample cannot be transferred directly to other lithologies, because there is a relationship between porosity, permeability and ultrasonic parameters. Goueygou et al. (2003) concluded, that the correlation between physical and acoustic parameters of sound materials features the trend: velocity decreases with porosity and permeability whereas attenuation increases for dry samples and decreases for saturated samples.

This knowledge gives an idea of the AE-rod's limitations and facilitates the data analysis. However, the designed AE-rod, based on various experiments, seems to be a strong tool to acquire AE data. The testing in the field showed clearly that the AE-rod itself does not generate considerable AE events, but it captures external AE signals. The first results of the acquired data are promising and point to a successful design, construction and installation of AE-rod. Concerning the difference in AE activity between *top site* (very dry) and *bottom site* (lot of water), there appears to be evidence that the

AE activity in hard intact rock strongly depends on the combination of water availability and subzero temperatures. But to analyze and interpret the acquired data carefully and get meaningful statements, the time period with useful measurements is too short and thus does not represent the *in situ* conditions all year long. Furthermore, the moisture data at depth are missing due to the missing capacitance measurements.

Moreover, the analyses of the AE signal have to be interpreted with reserve. AE events might be caused by external influences like small rock/ice falls, in our case in a radius of approximately 1 m. The direct comparison of the results from Jungfraujoeh with the theoretical and experimental investigations of e.g., Murton, Hallet and their co-workers might be difficult, because the formation of cracks and thus the generation of AE events happens suddenly, randomly and in bursts. Further Murton, Hallet and their co-workers used porous lime- and sandstones, but the lithology of the field site on Jungfraujoeh is gneiss. Thus, on the one hand, the choice of a field site in mountain permafrost with lime- or sandstone would have been a good alternative. On the other hand, the generation of new, visible cracks in hard intact rocks have not been proved yet and thus a remaining key question is if hard intact rocks are only damaged by frost (cf. Matsuoka & Murton, 2008). Further, most of the high mountain environments feature jointed hard rock. Therefore, the performed measurements in gneiss might advance the frost weathering comprehension.

Even if this measurement assembly was designed for AE measurements in steep cold rock-walls, it can be installed anywhere in hard rock (i.e., magmatic and metamorphic bedrock), or at least in compact rock in which the gluing and sealing procedure works. For soft or porous rock, the installation procedure has to be adapted in order to prevent that all pores and fissures get filled. This is necessary at least for the moisture probe, because there is no space for water if all close pores and fissures are filled.

The findings of this thesis point toward the following questions and research needs:

- For the interpretation of the field measurements, an extended characterization of the field site (e.g., cleft frequency, surface roughness, angle of anisotropy relative to exposition) can be useful.
- To generate AE pulses with one sensor (stronger source than *Field-CAL*) and to measure AE with the second one might enable to deter-

mine temporal changes in the layers between.

- In the case of using a waveguide, the influence of sealing on the waveform has to be checked. Further the Experiment 4 has to be repeated using an aluminum waveguide.
- Another application using AE would be the combination of AE and crack meter measurements.
- Compare the resistance data of Andreas Hasler's sensor rods (cf. Hasler, 2011) with the moisture data based on capacity measurements (*Sentek EnviroSMART* probe).

The main results of this Master's thesis will be presented at the *Tenth International Conference on Permafrost* (TICOP) and a paper is submitted for publishing in the conference proceedings. The draft of the submitted paper is attached in the Appendix C.

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A Appendix

A.1 Equations

Clausius-Clapeyron Equation (Williams & Smith, 1989)

$$\frac{dT}{dP} = \frac{T_m}{(\rho_w - \rho_i) \cdot L_f} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

- ρ_w density of water [kg m^{-3}]
 ρ_i density of ice [kg m^{-3}]
 L_f heat of fusion of ice [J kg^{-1}]
 T_m normal freezing point ($0^\circ \text{C} = 273.15 \text{K}$)
 dP change of pressure
 dT change of freezing point

Derivation of attenuation coefficient α_{linear}

Based on the $A^{\text{SI}}-A^{\text{dB}}$ -conversion,

$$A^{\text{dB}} = 20 \cdot \log_{10} (A^{\text{SI}}) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

the attenuation coefficient α is derived from Equation 2.15:

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\text{SI}} &= A_0^{\text{SI}} e^{-\alpha r} \\ \log_{10} \left(\frac{A^{\text{SI}}}{A_0^{\text{SI}}} \right) &= \log_{10} (e^{-\alpha r}) \\ \log_{10} (A^{\text{SI}}) - \log_{10} (A_0^{\text{SI}}) &= \frac{-\alpha r}{\ln(10)} \\ \frac{A^{\text{dB}}}{20} - \frac{A_0^{\text{dB}}}{20} &= \frac{-\alpha r}{\ln(10)} \\ A^{\text{dB}} - A_0^{\text{dB}} &= \frac{20}{\ln(10)} (-\alpha r) \\ \alpha &= \frac{(A_0^{\text{dB}} - A^{\text{dB}}) \ln(10)}{r \cdot 20} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where α is in Np/m. Using the α [Np/m]- α [dB]-conversion,

$$\alpha[\text{dB}] = \frac{20}{\ln(10)} (\alpha[\text{Np/m}]) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

α in dB/m can be expressed as:

$$\alpha = \frac{A_0^{\text{dB}} - A^{\text{dB}}}{r} = \frac{\Delta A^{\text{dB}}}{r} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

whereby α is in Np/m is exponential and α in dB/m is linear (see Figure A.1)

Figure A.1: Amplitude A as a function of distance r .

A.2 Sketches and Technical Drawings

Figure A.2: Sketch of the installation setting for two AE-rods at 10 cm and 50 cm depth (scale 1 : 5).

Figure A.3: Sketch of the installation setting for an AE-rod at 10 cm depth (scale 1 : 1).

Pos 10

10	1			Abstandhalter_DM40	POM	
Pos.	Menge	Einheit	Sachnummer	Benennung/Merkmale		
And.			And.	Gezeichnet	R. Maier	Massstab
				E-Mail	maier@physik.uzh.ch	1:1
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A.3 Drill Core Analysis

Table A.1 gives an overview of the the porosity of all drill cores for the different probes but the *Th3*, because its drill core was broken too many times. Figure A.4 shows pictures of the different drill cores, whereby the *Th3* drill cores are missing.

Table A.1: Relative porosity of the drill cores.

Site	Probe	Depth range [cm]	Porosity ^a [vol%]	Density ^b [kg/dm ³]	
Top site	AE1	0–18	0.7	2.78	
		AE2	0–14	0.9	2.68
	22–33		0.5	2.68	
	47–53		0.7	3.01	
	Sentek	0–8	1.6	2.93	
		45–50	0.8	2.72	
		82–87	0.6	2.75	
		120–125	0.6	2.74	
	Bottom site	AE1	0–9	0.6	2.73
			9–15	0.7	2.56
AE2		0–8	0.8	2.67	
		8–15	1.0	2.72	
		<i>approx.</i> 35	1.0	2.79	
		<i>approx.</i> 50	0.8	2.78	
Sentek		10–12	1.6	2.64	
		20–25	1.3	2.79	
		40–52	0.7	2.73	

^a Uncertainty is approximately 0.04 vol%

^b Uncertainty is approximately 0.02 kg/dm³

Figure A.4: Drill cores of the different probe holes.

A.4 Addresses and Contacts

Relevant addresses and contacts are listed here:

Blétry AG Benkenstrasse 52, 5024 Küttigen, Switzerland.

HFSJG Hochalpine Forschungsstation, 3801 Jungfrauojoch, Switzerland.

Kümpel AG Poststrasse 10, 6060 Sarnen, Switzerland.

Physical Acoustics A Mistras holding company, Postfach 701344, 22013 Hamburg, Germany.

Sofranel 59, rue Parmentiern, 78500 Sartrouville, France.

A.5 Material Specifications and Properties

Table A.2 shows the specification of the used metals and Table A.3 gives an overview of the properties of all investigated material candidates.

Table A.2: Specification of the used metals.

	<i>Alloy</i>	<i>Norm</i>
Aluminum	6060 AlMgSi	EN AW-6060, EN 573-3
Mild steel	EN 10027-2 (S235JRG2C)	DIN EN 10025
Ni-Cr-steel	1.4301 / AISI 304	X5CrNi18-10

Table A.3: Properties of material candidates.

Material	Density [kg/m ³]	Young modulus ^a [GPa]	Poisson ratio ^b	Velocity C ₁ [m/s]	Acoustic impedance ^c Z ₁ [SI]	Transmission coefficient T	Attenuation coefficient α [dB/m]
Mild steel	7900	200	0.3	5838	46.1 · 10 ⁶	0.71	30
Aluminum	2700	70	0.35	6451	17.4 · 10 ⁶	0.99	10
Ni-Cr-steel	7900	200	0.3	5838	46.1 · 10 ⁶	0.71	60
POM C	1420	3	0.35	1841	2.61 · 10 ⁶	0.53	71
RESIDUR Geo-Gel	1020	0.1	0.45	610	0.62 · 10 ⁶	0.16	151
Gneiss	2700	56	0.28	5149	13.9 · 10 ⁶	1	35

^a Young's modulus is a measure of the stiffness and is defined as the ration of the uniaxial stress over the uniaxial strain in the range of stress in which Hooke's Law holds.

^b Poisson's ratio is the ratio when a sample object is stretched, of the contraction or transverse strain to the extension or axial strain.

^c SI unit of acoustic impedance: kg/(s · m²)

A.6 Equipment Specifications

FieldCALTM – Portable AE Calibrator (MISTRAS Group Inc.)

Size (<i>L</i> × <i>W</i> × <i>H</i>):	5.5" × 3.25" × 1.375" (14 cm × 8.25 cm × 3.5 cm)
Weight:	0.5 lbs (225 g) including batteries
Power Source:	2 – AA batteries
Battery Life:	> 20 days of typical use
Output Waveforms:	Continuous Sinewave, Sinewave Burst, simulated AE signal
Output Frequencies:	30 kHz, 60 kHz, 150 kHz, 300 kHz
Sinewave Burst Duration:	100 μs, 1 ms, 10 ms
AE signal:	100 μs rise time, 200 μs duration with threshold – 20 dB at 150 kHz frequency.
Amplitude Range:	30 dB to 90 dB in 10 dB steps
Accuracy:	±0.5 dB Amplitude, ±2% Timing & Frequency
Repetition Rate:	1, 10, 100 per second or Manual trigger
Signal to Noise Ratio:	> 60 dB
Waveform DAC:	14 bit
Operating Temperature:	–15° F – –158° F (–20° C to + 55° C)
Storage Temperature:	–40° F – 185° F (–40° C to + 85° C)
Certifications:	CE EN 1000-4-2 ESD, EN 1000-4-3 RFI, EN 1000-4-4 EFT EN 55011 Emissions EN 61010 Safety

R6α Sensor

General Purpose, 60 kHz Resonant
Frequency Acoustic Emission Sensor

Description and Features

The Alpha series family of sensors features SMA connectors versus the Microdot connectors found on PAC's RXX series of passive sensors. The Alpha series includes R3α, R6α, R15α, R30α, R50α, R80α and WSα sensors. The major improvements in Alpha series over the RXX series include:

- Use of the more popular SMA type of connector.
- Cavity is machined from a solid stainless steel rod making for a simpler and more robust design.
- Dramatically increased thickness of the ceramic shoe for better mechanical stability.
- Distance from the bottom of the ceramic shoe to the bottom edge of sensor cavity increased for better insulation resistance and ground avoidance.
- Introduced a 30-degree angle at the bottom edge of the sensor cavity.

All these improvements make the Alpha series sensors more robust, reliable and greatly reduce the possible grounding of the cavity to the structure caused by wet environment.

Application

This sensor can be used on metal and FRP structures such as pipelines or storage tanks in petroleum, refineries, chemical plants, and offshore platforms, due to its high sensitivity and low resonance frequency properties.

Frequency response of the R6α. Calibration based on ASTM E1106; Calibration based on ASTM E976.

Operating Specifications

Dynamic

Peak Sensitivity V/(m/s); [V/μbar] 75 [-64] dB
Operating Frequency Range 35 - 100 kHz
Resonant Freq. V/(m/s); [V/μbar] 55 [90] kHz
Directionality ±1.5 dB

Environmental

Temperature Range -65 to 175°C
Shock Limit 500 g
Completely enclosed crystal for RFI/EMI immunity	

Physical

Dimensions 0.75" dia. x 0.88" h (19 x 22.4 mm)
Weight 38 grams
Case Material Stainless Steel
Face Material Ceramic
Connector SMA
Connector Locations Side
Seal Epoxy
Sensor to Preamp Cable (1 or 2 meters) 1232-X-SMA

Ordering Information and Accessories

R6α R6α or R6α
Magnetic Hold-Down MHR15A
Preamplifier 0/2/4, 2/4/6
Preamp to System Cable (specify length in meters) 1234 - X

Sensors include

NIST Calibration Certificate & Warranty

195 Clarksville Road, Princeton Junction, NJ 08550 • Phone: 609-716-4000
Fax: 609-716-0706 • Email: sales.systems@mistrasgroup.com • Internet: www.mistrasgroup.com

PK61 Sensor

Medium Frequency Integral Preamplifier Resonant Acoustic Emission Sensor

Description and Features

The PK61 sensor is a medium frequency, resonant, acoustic emission sensor with an integral, ultra low noise, low power, filtered, 26dB preamplifier, which can drive up to 200 meters of cable. This sensor represents an improvement in both noise and low power consumption performance, with noise level below 3 μ V and power consumption of 25 mW. The PK61 features a strong stainless steel, integrated body structure. The sensor has smaller size and the same frequency response as the R61 sensor.

The integrated Auto Sensor Test (AST*) capability allows these sensors to pulse as well as receive. This feature lets you verify the sensor coupling and performance at any time before, during or after the test.

Applications

The PK61 sensor has been designed to be used with the Pocket AE, a small handheld AE system, or with the Sensor Highway II, an outdoor rated, on-line monitoring system.

* AST -- Auto Sensor Testing feature allows AE systems to control the sensor as a pulser and a receiver at the same time. It can therefore characterize its own condition as well as send out a simulated acoustic emission wave that other sensors can detect, so the condition of the nearby sensors also can be tested.

Operating Specifications

Dynamic

Peak Sensitivity, Ref V/(m/s)	106 dB
Operating Frequency Range	35 to 65 kHz
Resonant Frequency, Ref V/(m/s).....	~55 kHz
Directionality.....	+/- 1.5 dB

Environmental

Temperature Range	-35° to 80° C
Shock Limit	500 g

Physical

Dimensions.....	0.812D X 1.06H/20.6 X 27
Weight	45 grams
Case Material.....	Stainless Steel
Face Material.....	Ceramic
Connector	SMA
Connector Locations	side

Electrical

Input Power Range (VDC)	4 to 7
Operating/Max Current (mA)	5/35
Internal Preamp Gain	26 dB
RMS Noise RTI (referred to input).....	< 3 μ V

Ordering Information and Accessories

PK61	PK61
Cable (specify cable length)	1234-SMA/BNC-X
Magnetic Hold-Down	MHPK151
Amplifier Subsystem	AE2A, AE5A

Sensors include

NIST Calibration Certificate & Warranty

195 Clarksville Road, Princeton Junction, NJ 08550
 Phone: 609-716-4000 • Fax: 609-716-0706 •
 Email: sales.systems@mistrasgroup.com • www.mistrasgroup.com

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#64-08

**PRELIMINARY
SENSOR DATA SHEET**

DATE: September 29, 2001

R15UG SENSOR Type

- **DESCRIPTION:** The R15UG sensor family is an electrically insulated under ground/water sensor with 150 kHz resonance frequency. The body of the sensor is covered with epoxy to insure the insulation and sealing between sensor and surrounding environment.
- **APPLICATION:** The sensor is specially designed for under ground/water application. The maximum allowable water pressure of this sensor still needs to be verified by experimentation. The recommended maximum pressure is 50 psi.

R15UG Type sensor with top cable exit

Mechanical Specifications:

Dimensions	Weight (g)	Temperature (°C)	Shock (g)	Case material	Face material	Connector type	Connector location
0.69”d x 0.69”h (1.73 x 1.73 cm)	-	- 45 to 100° C	500 g	Epoxy covered stainless steel	ceramic	BNC	Top Integral cable side

Sensor Performance Specifications

Peak sensitivity Ref(V/(m/s)/Ref [V/mbar]	Oper frequency range(kHz)	Resonance frequency (kHz)	Directionality (dB)	Grounding	Seal type
69 [-64]	50 –200	70[150]	+/- 1.5	Case grounded and isolated from mounting surface	Epoxy

All specifications are subject to change without notice.

OPTIONS:

- Cable length can be varied according customer requirement.
- Side cable option available

Sensor Name: R15UG Type **Test Date:** **Max. Value (dB):** -62.48
Sensor S/N: **Tested By:** **Peak Freq.(kHz):** 152.34
Comment: This is an R15UG type sensor with top connector.

PAC Certifies that this sensor meets all performance, environmental and physical standards established in applicable PAC specifications. Calibration methodology based on ASTM standard E1106-“Standard Method for Primary Calibration of Acoustic Emission Sensors.”

USB Acoustic Emission (AE) Node

Easy Laptop & PC Connection and Low Cost AE System with Free LabView/C++ Driver

USB AE Node

The USB AE Node is a single channel Acoustic Emission (AE) Digital Signal Processor with full AE hit and time based features, including waveforms. Through the USB Connector, the AE Node is easily interfaced to a Notebook or PC running Windows XP™ and Physical Acoustics Corporation (PAC) well known AEwin™ or AEwin Lite™. The USB AE nodes can be connected to available USB ports of a notebook or a USB hub for multi-channel operation.

The AE Node can accept single ended or differential sensors amplified by an internal low noise preamplifier. Additionally, PK Series low power integral preamp sensors can be used for long distance connections.

"AEwin for USB" AE NODE Software

Extracted Hit Features:

Time of 1st Threshold Crossing
Peak Amplitude, Energy, Envelope Strength, Duration, Rise Time, Counts, True Energy, RMS, ASL, Counts to Peak Parametrics (1-2)

Time Based Features

ASL, RMS, True Energy, Parametrics (1-4)

Features & Benefits

- Powered and operated through USB Port
- Rugged surface mount (SMT) construction
- Built-in internal preamplifier and power for external preamplifiers
- 18 bit resolution, 20MHz sampling frequency
- With analog and programmable digital filters
- Waveform and Location Options
- Free LabView/C++ driver available for customer program development

Specifications

AE Input:	1 Channel per USB node
Sampling Frequency:	20 MHz
AE Digitizing:	18 bits
Parametric Inputs:	CH 1, +/- 10V, 16 bits CH 2-4, 0-10V, 16 bits
Digital I/O:	2
Preamplifier:	Built-in
OS:	Windows XP or Vista
Case Size:	L5.25" x W3.25" x H1.25" (133 x 83 x 32mm)
Weight:	0.5 lbs. (0.23kg)
Power Consumption:	< 0.5 watt

195 Clarksville Road, Princeton Junction, NJ 08550 USA
Phone: (609) 716-4000 • Fax: (609) 716-0706
Email: sales.systems@mistrasgroup.com • www.mistrasgroup.com

FieldCal

Acoustic Emission Hand-held, Battery Powered Signal Generator

MISTRAS Products & Systems newest addition to our line of Acoustic Emission (AE) products is the FieldCAL, a low cost, small hand held battery powered AE signal generator. This unit can produce all the AE signals necessary to verify the correct operation of AE sensors, preamplifiers and AE systems. Five different waveforms are pre-programmed into the unit including Standard AE Waveforms, 3 Tone Bursts and continuous sine waves. Output amplitude can be set in 10dB increments from 30dB to 90dB, with a choice of four different frequencies covering the AE range. The output level of the FieldCAL is adjustable to the signal level of an AE sensor, a 26dB or a 40dB preamplifier.

The FieldCAL unit operates for approximately one month of daily use on two standard AA batteries. The membrane switch overlay protects the system from dirt and grime in the field and LEDs allow for easy use in low light environments.

Features:

- Easy to use, easy to set-up
- Maintains previous settings on power-up.
- Small Handheld battery powered system
- Compatible with standard AE sensors, preamplifiers and systems.
- Can be used for the verification of AE sensors, preamplifiers and systems.
- Can also be used as a pulse or waveform generator for Acousto-Ultrasonics or guided wave applications.
- Uses two standard AA batteries providing approximately one month of daily use.
- Generates five types of AE calibration signals, i.e. a standard AE signal with calibrated rise and fall time; three tone burst sine wave with length in 100 μ s, 1 ms and 10 ms respectively; a continuous sine wave.
- Outputs AE waveforms at four frequencies: 30 kHz, 60 kHz, 150 kHz and 300 kHz.
- Outputs AE waveforms at seven different amplitudes. Peak waveform amplitude can be set for 30dB, 40dB, 50dB, 60dB 70dB, 80dB or 90dB.
- Outputs AE waveforms at four different repetition rates: 1 pps, 10 pps, 100 pps and manual trigger.
- Three user selectable test ranges including a range for a sensor, a 26dB preamplifier and a 40dB preamplifier.

FieldCAL AE Signal Generator

A Appendix

FieldCAL

FieldCAL Specifications

Size:	(L x W x H) 4.75" x 3" x 1.25" (120 x 75 x 32) mm
Weight:	0.42 lbs (190 g)
Power Requirements:	2 - AA Batteries
Battery Life:	One month typical daily use
Waveform Types:	Sine wave Burst, Continuous Sine, AE Signal
Sine Wave Burst Duration:	100 μ s, 1ms, 10ms
AE Waveform:	100 μ s rise time, 100 μ s fall time with threshold -20dB at a frequency of 150 kHz
Amplitude range:	30dB to 90dB in 10 dB steps
Repetition Rate:	1, 10, 100 signals per second or Manual Trigger
Signal to Noise Ratio:	> 60dB
Operating Temperature:	-15° - 158°F (-20° - 55°C)
Storage Temperature:	-40° - 185°F (-40° - 85°C)

FieldCal with Pocket AE Portable Acoustic Emission System

MISTRAS is a team of skilled researchers, engineers, technicians and manufacturing personnel dedicated to the development of practical and cost saving solutions for your challenging inspection and monitoring needs.

For additional information, please contact our Princeton Junction headquarters at 609-716-4000.

Approvals

Certified to the following standards:

CE Mark

EN 1000-4-2 ESD, EN 1000-4-3 RFI, EN 1000-4-4 EFT,

EN 55011 Emissions, EN 61010 Safety

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B Practical Recommendation

The idea of this practical recommendation is to pass on the acquired knowledge to get useful AE data after a field installation. The following description shows the most important steps to reproduce a complete AE measurement set-up:

Scouting

The scouting of possible field sites facilitates the following installation campaign. For an easier interpretation of the generated data, various factors (e.g., surface curvature, slope, exposition, water availability, lithology etc.) should be in the same order of magnitude for micro (mm – cm) and macro (dm – Dm) scale. If there are more than one field site, they should be distinguished only by one factor. Otherwise, a possible difference in the result cannot be explained easily.

Drill campaign

For the drill campaign, installing a platform increase work comfort and practicability. By using hollow core drilling, the drill cores can be analyzed afterwards. Independent the kind of drill, the end of the bore hole has to be made flat.

Drilling cores

The resulting cores can be characterized and analyzed in the lab. For this, the cores have to be stored and described properly and if they break, the depth has to be marked. To transport them and to avoid that the different parts get mixed, a box with the same width as the drill core diameter is advisable.

Coupling sensor

To get a reliable contact between sensor and medium, the sensor has to be rotated many times until the air has moved away. Even with rotating, the repetition of the coupling at the same place can already generate a variation of 2 – 3 dB (personal communication Mr. Manuel Löhr, Physical Acoustic, August 23, 2011).

Characterization

An exact field site characterization is important to interpret and compare the resulting data. A suggestion is given in section 3.2.4, but it has to be adapted depending on the research question.

Gluing and sealing

For reliable AE acquisition, take care that the drilling hole is still dry during the gluing and sealing phase. For this, you can use a water vacuum cleaner and suck the water out. To dry the borehole properly, you can blow in warm air generated by a gas burner or a hot air gun. To avoid the penetration of water in the hole, it can be covered using a plastic that is fixed with screws on the rock and sealed with Silicon. Afterwards during gluing, the AE-rod has to be fixed in the hole (e.g., using wooden wedges) until the glue is hardened. Otherwise, if you move the glue during drying or if it gets wet, the contact between rock and AE-rod is much worse or even unusable. During the sealing phase, the borehole still has to be dry, because already a small amount of water mixed with *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* changes its properties. For the injection of the *RESIDUR Geo-Gel*, a customary applicator gun, a cartridge filled with the *RESIDUR Geo-Gel* and a long thin metal tube can be used.

Installation of electronics

The necessary electronics (e.g., AE-box, sensor nodes etc.) should be placed and fixed next to the installation. Further the cable should be protected with a plastic tube. But all additional installation on the rock surface should not alter the measurement site too much (e.g., not causing shadow or collecting snow).

Time management

The time schedule has to be adequate. That mean to take account of enough time, beginning with the production of the AE-rod over the scouting to the final installation, because the lead time or bad weather condition can delay or even endanger the whole campaign.

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Design of a Measurement Assembly to Study In-Situ Rock Damage Driven by Freezing

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Abstract

We describe the design of an acoustic emission (AE) measurement assembly for reliable acquisition of a multi-year time-series in steep alpine rock-walls. Motivations for these measurements are the understanding of freezing-induced rock damage. Because measurements in natural rock slopes are challenging, this study investigates technical options suitable to capture AE signals from differing depths while incurring minimal signal loss between the rock and the sensor. We first outline the requirements for the measurement assembly, present two generic solutions to be evaluated and refined. We then present candidate materials for building parts of the assembly and experimentally estimate their attenuation coefficients and the signal loss at the rock-sensor contact. Based on these results we present the final design chosen for the measurement assembly and briefly report first experiences from a field deployment at 3500 m a.s.l at Jungfrauoch, Switzerland.

Keywords: Acoustic emissions; measurement assembly; depth; mountain permafrost; rock fracturing.

Introduction

In cold regions, ice formation is known to be an important driver of rock fracturing (Matsuoka & Murton 2008) and commonly referred to as frost weathering. The formation of ice in rock induces pressure variations in rock pores and cracks, which can cause damage near the surface as well as at a depth of up to several meters (Murton *et al.* 2006). This process may be crucial for the slow preconditioning of rock fall from warming permafrost areas (Gruber & Haerberli 2007). Most knowledge about the associated processes stems from theoretical studies (Walder & Hallet 1985) or laboratory experiments (Murton *et al.* 2006). However the transfer of corresponding insights to natural conditions, involving strong spatial and temporal heterogeneity, is nontrivial.

The monitoring of acoustic emissions (AE) is a powerful technique to track the evolution of damage. AE signals are transient elastic waves generated by the release of energy during rapid local changes of inelastic strains in solid materials. These events are accompanied by damage increase or to shearing of existing fractures (Scholz 1968). AE monitoring has been used at the rock sample scale (Lockner 1993) in laboratory studies, and under natural conditions to monitor seismicity and rock bursts in mines and tunnels as well as slope instabilities (Amitrano *et al.* 2005). In a four-day experiment, Amitrano *et al.* (2011) used AE monitoring to investigate freezing-induced rock damage in a high-elevation rock slope. There, AE activity was more intense during freezing periods and in locations subject to diurnal flow of melt water from snow patches.

To better understand rock damage under natural conditions, continuous AE monitoring and the ability to estimate source depths of events are desirable. We expect the investigation of diurnal and seasonal cycles as well as rock in an advanced stage of pre-fracturing to be

important for the robust scaling of theoretical insight to field conditions. In this paper we describe the design of an AE measurement assembly for reliable acquisition of a multi-year time-series in steep alpine rock-walls relying on commercial sensors. Because measurements in natural rock slopes are challenging, this study investigates technical options suitable to capture AE signals from differing depths while incurring minimal signal loss between the rock and the sensor.

We first outline the requirements for the measurement assembly, present two generic solutions to be evaluated and refined, and based on this derive the problems to be addressed in detail. We then present candidate materials for building parts of the assembly and experimentally estimate their attenuation coefficients and the signal loss at the rock-sensor contact. Based on these results we present the final design chosen for the measurement assembly and briefly report first experiences from a field deployment at 3500 m a.s.l at Jungfrauoch, Switzerland.

Requirements and problem statement

The assembly to be designed shall enable a reliable, consistent and repeatable measurement. The spatial scale of rock considered is on the order of one meter, with flaw sizes of millimeters. At the scale of one meter, variations of temperature and ice-induced stress are expected to dominantly occur along the dimension of depth, oriented normal to the rock surface. The use of two sensors, installed at differing depths could provide a *zonation* of the source depths. While installing more than two sensors may provide more accurate localization, it considerably increases disturbance of the rock, and cost involved.

Measuring at depth requires a borehole. Two methods are then considered for capturing the AE signal: (i) insertion of the sensor into the borehole, or (ii) insertion of a waveguide for transmitting the signal to the rock

surface, where the sensor is installed. Water flow in the borehole can alter moisture conditions at depth and thus cause spurious AE events related to freezing/thawing (Kaufmann 1999). To avoid such events the borehole must be sealed after installation. To enable long-term measurements, the possibility to exchange sensors in the borehole is desired. Based on these requirements, we propose two generic designs for the measurement assembly to be tested and refined (Fig. 1):

(i) The construction of a **casing**, which accommodates the sensor within the borehole. The rock-sensor contact is made using a thin plate glued to the bottom of the borehole. While the AE signal transmission should be good for this conductive plate other parts of the casing should exhibit strong attenuation to avoid pollution by acoustic events originating from different depths. The casing has to be made waterproof and extends to the rock surface where a lid allows signal extraction as well as sensor exchange.

(ii) A **waveguide**-based solution uses a thin rod fixed to the bottom of a borehole and a sensor installed on top above the rock surface. The sensor requires mechanical protection to prevent damage from rock fall or icing.

We investigate the feasibility of both solutions, and evaluate their impact on the measured AE signal.

Fig. 1: The two generic measurement assemblies: Casing and waveguide

Background

As a basis for investigating suitable materials, we briefly review the propagation of elastic waves in solids, for simplicity only considering compression waves (p-waves). Assuming a homogeneous, isotropic medium, the compressional velocity of elastic waves is given by (e.g. Hardy 2003),

$$C = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho} \frac{(1-\nu)}{(1+2\nu)(1+\nu)}} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density, E the Young modulus and ν the Poisson ratio. The acoustic impedance related to p-waves can then be defined as,

$$Z = \rho C \quad (2)$$

The transmission coefficient between two different materials with acoustic impedances Z_a and Z_b can then be calculated,

$$T = 1 - \left(\frac{Z_a - Z_b}{Z_a + Z_b} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

The largest transmission of the elastic wave occurs therefore between materials that have similar acoustic impedances. Another property that needs to be accounted for in the choice of the materials is the attenuation coefficient. As an elastic wave propagates from a source through a medium, amplitude decrease due to absorption can be estimated as:

$$A^l = A_0^l e^{-\alpha r} \quad (4)$$

where A_0^l is the linear amplitude at the source, A^l that at a distance r from the source, and α is the frequency-dependent attenuation coefficient.

Candidate materials and their evaluation

Candidate materials for the measurement assembly

Two categories of materials are needed for the assembly: transmitting and attenuating materials. The transmitting materials should have a low impedance mismatch with the rock (i.e. large transmission coefficient) and a small attenuation coefficient, while the damping materials should have the opposite properties: low transmission coefficient and large attenuation.

As transmitting candidate materials we considered ordinary mild steel, chromium steel and aluminum, because metals are typically good acoustic transmitters. For the damping material, we selected a thermoplastic polymer called POM-C (DuPont Delrin). We also examined the physical properties of a two-component polyurethane-resin (Geo-Gel from Kuempel AG, Sarnen, Switzerland). This is a slow-hardening resin with a viscosity of 850 mPa·s (i.e. between olive oil and liquid honey). It could thus be injected in the borehole after the installation of the measurement assembly in order to seal the hole. Finally, the properties of gneiss (from Ticino, Switzerland) were considered as representative of those of the rock at the planned field site.

Table 1 reports the mechanical properties of these materials. The speed of sound, acoustic impedance, and transmission coefficient within gneiss were calculated as detailed above. Considering these results, aluminum appears as the best candidate material to build the rock-sensor contact. In the 'casing-based-solution' this contact is made through a thin metal plate, while in the 'waveguide-based-solution' the contact is made through the waveguide itself. The results also suggest that POM-C is suitable to build the casing, as it shows a low transmission coefficient with gneiss. Similarly the Geo-Gel shows a low transmission coefficient when applied to gneiss. Its use as a sealing agent would thus provide further reflection and attenuation of spurious AE signals.

Table 1. Material properties.

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Young modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Speed of sound C (m/s)	Acoustic impedance Z (SI)	Transmission coefficient T	Attenuation coefficient α (dB/m)
Mild steel	7900	200	0.3	5838	46.1 10 ⁶	0.71	30
Aluminum	2700	70	0.35	6451	17.4 10 ⁶	0.99	10
Chromium steel	7900	200	0.3	5838	46.1 10 ⁶	0.71	60
POM C	1420	3	0.35	1841	2.61 10 ⁶	0.53	71
Geo-Gel	1020	0.1	0.45	610	0.62 10 ⁶	0.16	151
Gneiss	2700	56	0.28	5149	13.9 10 ⁶	1	35

Experimental determination of the attenuation coefficient

To facilitate comparison, the attenuation coefficients of candidate materials were determined experimentally (Figure 2). This was achieved using two AE sensors with a given spacing placed on a sample of each material. An artificial source was applied and the amplitude of the resulting stress wave monitored with both AE sensors. The source was either a FieldCal pulser (Physical Acoustics Limited, UK) or the breaking of 0.5 mm pencil lead. The frequency of the FieldCal was set to 60 kHz, the resonant frequency of the AE sensors used. The AE sensors and the FieldCal were coupled to the rock using an ultrasonic coupling gel (UCA2 from Sofranel, France). The attenuation coefficient, as defined by Eq. 4, can then be calculated as $\alpha = \Delta A/d$, where ΔA is the measured amplitude difference (in dB) between the AE sensors separated by distance d . The results, reported in Table 1, suggest that mild steel and aluminum have lower attenuation coefficients than chromium steel. Damping materials showed indeed higher attenuation coefficients, with that of Geo-Gel being about one order of magnitude higher than that of the metals.

Fig. 2: Experimental set-up for determination of the attenuation coefficient

Attenuation of the rock-sensor contact

Signal loss at the rock-sensor contact was determined experimentally (Figure 3) for the two possible solutions. Experiments were performed on a rectangular gneiss block (15 cm x 10 cm x 70 cm) using an artificial source and two receiving AE sensors (using ultrasonic coupling gel): a reference sensor, directly coupled to the rock and a test 'rock-sensor-contact'. The two sensors are at an equal distance from the source. The rock-sensor contacts tested are:

- (P1) a four-mm thick aluminum plate coupled to the rock with ultrasonic coupling gel;
- (P2) a four-mm thick aluminum plate glued to the rock;

- (WG1) a steel rod used as waveguide (10 mm diameter, 85 mm long) glued into the rock sample at 5 cm depth;
- (WG2) a steel rod used as waveguide (10 mm diameter, 85 mm long) fixed in the rock sample using an expansion anchor at 5 cm depth;
- (WG3) a steel rod used as waveguide (10 mm diameter, 120 mm long) glued into the rock sample at 2.5 cm depth; and
- (WG4) a steel rod used as waveguide (10 mm diameter, 420 mm long) glued into the rock sample at 2.5cm depth.

Fig. 3: Experimental set-up for determination of attenuation of the rock-sensor contact

Table 2 summarizes the loss in signal amplitude measured between the reference sensor and the different contacts investigated. The smallest attenuation is observed for contacts using a thin aluminum plate. While a simple coupling of the plate on the rock using the gel appears best in this laboratory experiment, this solution does not appear feasible in the field where the rock surface at the bottom of the borehole will be uneven. In this case the use of glue to fix the metal plate at the borehole bottom is likely a better solution. The waveguide-based contacts generally show larger attenuations. Fixing the waveguide using a glued interface extending over larger depth limits the attenuation but likely results in less accurate estimation of the source depths. Also, the use of an extension anchor to fix the waveguide should be avoided.

Table 2. Attenuation measured for different rock-sensor contacts.

	P1	P2	WG1	WG2	WG3	WG4
Mean attenuation (dB)	1.1	1.9	2.7	8.3	10	9.7
Standard deviation	0.3	0.7	0.8	1.8	1.1	1.3

Design and Test of the Measurement Assembly

Based on the experimental results, we designed the final measurement assembly using the ‘casing-based’ solution (Figure 4). The casing itself is made of a POM-C tube with an external diameter of 30 mm. It accommodates a piezoelectric sensor (R6alpha, Physical Acoustics Limited, UK) to record AE in the frequency range 1–150 kHz. The sensor (cylinder with 17 mm diameter, 17 mm height and a radial cable exit) is held down on the bottom assembly inside the casing using a spring. The bottom part of the casing is made of a four-mm thick aluminum plate. A lid with waterproof cable port completes the surface end of the casing. The assembly is glued to the bottom of the borehole only, and the remaining space sealed with a 5 mm-thick layer of Geo-Gel injected into void between borehole and casing.

Fig. 4: Installed AE-rod measurement assembly

A freeze-thaw experiment was performed with the first prototype of this assembly to evaluate the generation of spurious AE events due to the thermal expansion of the casing itself. In this experiment, the casing containing the AE sensor and a reference AE sensor were placed in a freezer and subjected to a temperature cycle from +20 °C to -15 °C and back to +20 °C. The amplitudes of measured AE events are shown in Figure 5. The results are difficult to interpret as the experimental setup was rather crude and it is likely that a fraction of the measured event were generated by the freezer itself.

Fig. 5: Result of freezer experiment: Temporal AE amplitude and temperature.

Four sensor-casing-assembly were installed in a rock-wall at Jungfrauoch (3500 m a.s.l.), in Switzerland. The strategy chosen for this deployment was to equip two contrasting sites with measurements at two different depths each. The boreholes were drilled at differing angles, aiming at a final alignment of the sensors normal to the rock surface (Figure 6). This reduces the disturbance caused by the boreholes in the rock closest to the AE sensors. The sensing parts of the casings are located at 10 and 50 cm depth.

The two sites equipped (Figure 7) are only ten meters apart and show similar general characteristics: southeasterly slope aspect, 50–70° steep rock wall of granitic gneiss. The main difference between these two sites lies in the availability of liquid water: while one site is on a rather dry spur-like feature, the second site is in a gully-like depression that collects melt-water from the surrounding snow patches.

Fig. 6: 2D sketch of field installation

In addition to the AE sensors, two probes to measure temperature and relative moisture (by capacitance) at different depth are installed at each site. Data, complemented by a webcam to document surface conditions, are transmitted through a wireless sensor network customized for operation in harsh environments (cf. Beutel *et al.* 2009; Hasler *et al.* 2011).

Fig. 7: Field site with installed equipment. The distance between the two equipped sites is approximately 10 m

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D Personal Declaration

I hereby declare that the submitted thesis is the result of my own, independent, work. All external sources are explicitly acknowledged in the thesis.

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